

A TIMURID EDUCATIONAL AND CHARITABLE FOUNDATION: THE IKHLĀṢIYYA COMPLEX OF ʿALĪ SHĪR NAVĀʿĪ IN 15TH-CENTURY HERAT AND ITS ENDOWMENT

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The Ikhḷāṣiyya, a major educational and charitable complex located in late 15th-century Herat (medieval eastern Khorasan; present-day northwest Afghanistan), was built and endowed by ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī, the great cultural patron and literary figure of the Timurid period, sometime between 881/1476–77 and 886 A.H./1481–82 A.D. Based on a neglected work in Chaghatay Turkish by ʿAlī Shīr himself, entitled simply *Vaqfiyya*, that represented a summary of various original documents of endowment pertaining to the complex, the article discusses the activities and personnel of the Ikhḷāṣiyya as well as the location and layout of its chief buildings. The lists it contains of ʿAlī Shīr’s private properties that he converted into pious endowments (*auqāf*) for the support and maintenance of the complex make the *Vaqfiyya* a unique source of information about the financial bases of his extensive patronage activity, while the data it provides on salaries and stipends and on the quantities of food distributed make it possible to estimate the actual size of the Ikhḷāṣiyya’s endowment. The description of the activities connected with the Ikhḷāṣiyya complex adds to our knowledge about the social and cultural life of late Timurid Herat and underscores the central role of the pious endowment (*vaqf*) in the formation of the remarkably productive period in the cultural history of medieval Iran and Central Asia that has often been referred to as the “Timurid renaissance.”

THE RELIGIOUS, EDUCATIONAL AND CHARITABLE INSTITUTIONS that formed the infrastructure of medieval Islamic society had their financial basis in the incomes from properties that had been declared mortmain and transferred to them by their owners. For although the physical premises of the myriad mosques (*masjid*), theological seminaries (*madrasa*), hostels (*khānaqāh*), way stations (*ribāʿ*), and the like could be constructed relatively cheaply and easily, given the availability of manpower and the ability of medieval potentates or

powerful landlords to mobilize it through such obligations as the corvée (Per. *biḡār*), it was the endowment established for their maintenance and for the support of the activities they housed that guaranteed their permanence and ensured their viability as social institutions.

The conditions for establishing a pious foundation (*vaqf*) differed from one school of Islamic law to another and by the late medieval period they had deviated considerably from classical Islamic theory. The most favorable conditions existed in the Hanafite school which predominated in Central Asia as well as in the Ottoman empire.¹ According to the more liberal

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¹ For the adoption of the Hanafite school of law among the nomadic Turks of Central Asia, see W. Heffening (-J. Schacht), “Ḥanafīyya,” in *The Encyclopaedia of Islam* [hereafter EI] (new ed., Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1960-), 3:162; I. P. Petrushevsky, *Islam in Iran*, trans. H. Evans (London: Athlone Press, 1985), 113. It ought to be noted that although the Shafʿite school was represented to some extent in the towns of eastern Iran, it was dominant in pre-Safavid times only in areas to the west of Khorasan, such as Azerbaijan, etc.; see Petrushevsky, *Islam in Iran*, 303.

interpretation of the later Hanafite jurists, as it developed precisely on the territory of Central Asia,² a *vaqf* could be constituted not only of immovable property, but also of movable property, the latter often embracing impermanent and even abstract income-producing sources, such as tax immunities.³ The endower of a *vaqf*, who had the right to stipulate all the terms and conditions of its use, could also name himself and his male descendants as its trustees (sg. *mutavallī*), thus creating a family endowment (*vaqf-i ahlī*), the benefits of which he and his family could continue to enjoy.⁴ Since *vaqf* properties were taxed at a much lower rate and could even be tax-free, and since in practice only a portion of the income from the endowment was actually disbursed for the maintenance of the pious institution for the benefit of which it had been set up, the trustees were in a position to enjoy the surplus income from it. In addition, since *vaqf* was legally inalienable, private property that had been converted into it was thus safeguarded against confiscation by the government—not an infrequent occurrence in the turbulent history of post-Mongol Iran and Central Asia.⁵

² On this, see Baber Johansen, *The Islamic Law on Land Tax and Rent: The Peasants' Loss of Property Rights as Interpreted in the Hanafite Legal Literature of the Mamluk and Ottoman Periods* (London: Croom Helm, 1988), 39–43.

³ See J. Krčsmárik, “Das Waqfrecht vom Standpunkte des Šarī‘atrechtes nach der ḥanefitischen Schule,” *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft*, 45 (1891): 529–30; also Robert D. McChesney, “Waqf at Balkh: A Study of the Endowments at the Shrine of ‘Alī Ibn Abī Ṭālib” (Ph.D. diss., Princeton University, 1973), 330. For the problem of the conversion or donation of tax immunities to pious endowments in Central Asia, see Maria Eva Subtelny, “Socioeconomic Bases of Cultural Patronage Under the Later Timurids,” *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 20, 4 (1988): 482–83.

⁴ On the admissibility of this practice, see W. Heffening, “Waqf,” in EI (1st ed., Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1913–38), 4:1097; Krčsmárik, “Das Waqfrecht,” 558–60; also I. P. Petrushevskii [= Petrushevsky], *Zemledelie i agrarnye otnosheniia v Irane XIII–XIV vekov* (Moscow-Leningrad, 1960), 247–48; and John Robert Barnes, *An Introduction to Religious Foundations in the Ottoman Empire* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1986), 12. The Maliki school, for example, prohibits the endower from retaining control of the trusteeship; see “Madrasa,” in EI (new ed.), 5:1129.

⁵ Ann K. S. Lambton, *Landlord and Peasant in Persia: A Study of Land Tenure and Land Revenue Administration* (Oxford, 1953; rep. ed., 1969), 113. See also Subtelny, “Socioeconomic Bases,” 483.

The practice of converting personal property into *vaqf* became extremely widespread in the second half of the 15th century during the reign of the Turko-Mongol dynasty of the Timurids, descendants of the nomadic conqueror, Tīmūr (Tamerlane), in the regions of Khorasan (corresponding roughly to present-day northeast Iran, south Turkmen S.S.R. and northwest Afghanistan) and Transoxania (present-day Uzbek S.S.R.).⁶ The existence of a very large fund of pious endowments at this time was already noted by contemporary authors, such as the historian, Khvāndamīr, who remarked that during the reign of the last great Timurid ruler, Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā (873–911/1469–1506), the number of pious endowments in Khorasan had become so great that it was no longer possible for a single individual to oversee them, thus necessitating the appointment of several persons simultaneously to the post of *ṣadr* (government official charged with overseeing all pious endowments in the Timurid realm).⁷

It was the growth of these pious endowments, as well as the increase in the distribution and confirmation of other fiscal privileges (especially the land grants with complete fiscal, administrative and judicial immunity, called *soyūrghāl*) that resulted in the expansion of the socio-economic bases of cultural patronage in the second half of the 15th century and that consequently gave rise to the cultural flowering of the late Timurid period.⁸

THE VAQFIYYA OF ‘ALĪ SHĪR NAVĀ’Ī

A striking illustration of the conversion of private property into *vaqf* during this period is provided by the career of the outstanding Timurid patron and political and cultural figure, Mīr ‘Alī Shīr Navā’ī (844–906/1441–1501).⁹ The scion of an Uighur family of *bakhshīs*

⁶ The same was true of the Ottoman empire at a slightly later period, ca. 1600–1800; see Barnes, *Introduction*, 42.

⁷ Ghiyāṣ al-Dīn Khvāndamīr, *Ḥabīb al-siyar*, ed. Jalāl al-Dīn Humā’ī, 4 vols. (Teheran, 1333/1954–55) [hereafter HS], 4:321. For the office of *ṣadr*, see Petrushevskii, *Zemledelie*, 249.

⁸ See Subtelny, “Socioeconomic Bases,” 485ff.

⁹ One of the most famous (or notorious, according to some scholars) and best documented examples of the conversion of personal property into family *vaqf* during this period were the extensive holdings of the Naqshbandi Sufi shaikh of Samarqand, Khvāja ‘Ubaidullāh Aḥrār (d. 1490); see the collection of his *vaqf* documents published by O. D. Chekhovich, ed. and trans., *Samarkandskie dokumenty XV–XVI vv. (O vladeniakh Khodzhi Akhrāra v Srednei Azii i Afganistane)* (Moscow, 1974).

(Turkic chancellery scribes), whose members had distinguished themselves in Timurid service, ʿAlī Shīr spent the better part of his life in the service of Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā, a descendant of Tīmūr's son, ʿUmar Shaikh, who ruled Khorasan from his capital, Herat.¹⁰

According to ʿAlī Shīr himself, who says he became rich from the produce of his lands, he was satisfied in his personal life with just a little food and clothing and, after covering such expenses as travel (*kelish barish*) on Ḥusain Bāyqarā's service, the salaries (*ʿulūfa*) of attendants and dependents, the outfitting of a military contingent (*cherik yaraghi*), provisioning (*muʿnāt*), and administrative dues (*taklīfāt*), he spent the rest of his personal fortune on public works and charitable institutions (*biqāʿ-i khair*).¹¹ His contemporary, the literary historian, Daulatshāh, estimated that the total value of all the properties he constituted as *vaqf* for the approximately 300 buildings, complexes and public works he built in Herat and throughout Khorasan was approximately 5 million *kapakī dīnārs*;¹² the historian suggested that he had been motivated by the desire to prevent his property from falling into the wrong hands.¹³

Among the buildings that ʿAlī Shīr constructed and endowed was a complex just outside Herat that, according to Daulatshāh, consisted of a congregational mosque (*masjid-i jāmiʿ*), a theological seminary (*madrassa*), a hostel (*khānaqāh*), a hospital (*dār al-shifā*) and a bath (*ḥammām*)—all located in one spot on the banks of the Injil canal.¹⁴ Bābur, the founder of the Moghul empire in India, who visited his Timurid cousins, the

sons of Ḥusain Bāyqarā, in Herat after the latter's death in 1506, reported that the congregational mosque was called "Qudsiyya," the seminary and hostel were called "Ikhlāsiyya" and "Khalāsiyya," respectively,¹⁵ and the hospital and bath were called "Shifāʿiyya" and "Ṣafāʿiyya," respectively. He also mentions ʿAlī Shīr's tomb (*maqbara*) and private residence, where he stayed during his visit and which he says was called "Unsiyya."¹⁶

Proof of the fact that ʿAlī Shīr considered this complex important is the short treatise he composed in 886/1481–82 in Chaghatay Turkish, entitled simply *Vaqfiyya*¹⁷ (but sometimes also variously referred to in manuscript catalogues as *Vaqfiyyāt*, *Vaqfiyya-i Ikhlāsiyya*, *Mauqūfāt-i Mir ʿAlī Shīr*, etc.), in which he relates how he acquired the land on which he built the complex, describes the location and layout of some of its buildings, enumerates the properties which he converted into *vaqf* for their support, and stipulates the conditions for their operation and maintenance. This treatise is not an official diploma of endowment, however, which would have been witnessed and registered with the Shariʿa law courts in order to establish the *vaqf* as legal. As a rule, such diplomas had to contain a precise delineation of the boundaries of the properties which were being constituted as *vaqf*, as well as proof that they had been acquired legally in accordance with the prescriptions of Islamic law. ʿAlī Shīr himself says on two separate occasions that his *Vaqfiyya* was merely a summary (*mujmal*) of the various original diplomas of endowment that he says were written in Persian (he refers to them as "*fārsī vaqfiyyalar*"), and that contained the particulars about these properties and were recorded in the qadis' registers (*quzāt sijillāti*).¹⁸

Since these documents do not appear to have survived, the *Vaqfiyya* represents an invaluable source of information about a Timurid pious foundation whose

¹⁰ For ʿAlī Shīr's background, see Maria Eva Subtelny, "ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī: *Bakhshī* and *Beg*," in *Eucharisterion: Essays Presented to Omeljan Pritsak on his Sixtieth Birthday*, ed. I. Ševčenko and F. Sysyn (= *Harvard Ukrainian Studies*, 3–4 [1979–80]), 2:799–802.

¹¹ ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī, *Vaqfiyya*, ms, Leningrad, State Public Library (Gosudarstvennaia Publichnaia Biblioteka im. M. E. Saltykova-Shchedrina), Khanykov, 55, fol. 115a (hereafter V [GPB]).

¹² Daulatshāh Samarqandī, *Tazkirat al-shuʿarā*, ed. Edward G. Browne (London: Luzac & Co., 1901) [hereafter TSh], 505. Daulatshāh gives the figure in *tūmāns* (1 *tūmān* being the equivalent of 10,000 *dīnārs*). For further corroborating evidence from contemporary sources, see Subtelny, "Socioeconomic Bases," 491 and 504, n. 119.

¹³ TSh, 505. Daulatshāh refers to them as "those who squander their inheritance and profit from windfalls" ("*mīrāḡ-khvārān va shaḡal-bārān*").

¹⁴ TSh, 505.

¹⁵ Bābur actually reversed the order of the names, calling the madrasa Khalāsiyya and the khanaqah Ikhlāsiyya. Khvāndamīr, on the other hand, is very explicit in stating which is which; see [Ghiyāḡ al-Dīn Khvāndamīr], *Faḡlī az Khulāṣat al-akhbār*, ed. Gūyā Iʿtimādī (Kabul, 1345/1966) [hereafter KhA], 19; so is ʿAlī Shīr himself; see below.

¹⁶ Zāhīr al-Dīn Muḥammad Bābur, *Bābur-nāma*, fac. ed. Annette S. Beveridge (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1905) [hereafter BN], fol. 191b.

¹⁷ The name of the work is contained in the author's versified colophon.

¹⁸ V(GPB), fol. 117a, ll. 26–27 and fol. 117b, ll. 20–21.

individual buildings have unfortunately not withstood the vicissitudes of time.¹⁹ The survival of the *Vaqfiyya* itself can be attributed to the fact that it was not a legal document, but was regarded primarily as a literary work—a fine specimen of classical Chaghatay prose—and, as such, was frequently appended to copies of ʿAlī Shīr’s major works, such as *Khamsa* (Quintet) or *Khazāʾin al-maʿānī* (the final edition of his four *dīvāns*), of which there are numerous manuscript copies still in existence,²⁰ or included in popular anthologies of his works.²¹ This is underscored by the fact that, although the complex figures prominently in the treatise, it does not represent its entire contents. In it ʿAlī Shīr also speaks of other personal matters: how he entered Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā’s service, the difficulties he encountered in government service, the reasons for his financial success, and his hopes and wishes for the future. The *Vaqfiyya* thus reads more like an apologia, with the complex and its endowment serving as a pretext for ʿAlī Shīr to voice some of his personal concerns.

Despite its value as a source for the social, cultural, and even economic history of the late Timurid period, the *Vaqfiyya* has never been the object of a separate scholarly study. The reason for this lies partly in the difficulty (at times, tortuousness) of its style, and partly in the unavailability of reliable published editions of the original Chaghatay text. A short excerpt from it in the Arabic script of the original (based on a MS in the Public Library of St. Petersburg) was included by I. Berezin in his Turkish chrestomathy, published in

Kazan in the second half of the 19th century.²² A popular edition of the work in Arabic script appeared in Baku in 1926. It was utilized by some researchers in the 1940s, but afterwards disappeared from scholarly circulation.²³ Subsequent editions did not appear until the 1960s when it was published (with minor omissions) in Tashkent in a popular edition of ʿAlī Shīr Navāʾī’s complete works in modern Uzbek transcription.²⁴ The Turkish scholar, Ağâh Sırrı Levend, in whose opinion the Baku edition was full of errors, published a shortened version in modern Turkish transcription (with summaries of the passages he omitted), based on MSS then held in the Topkapı Saray and Fatih libraries.²⁵ Unfortunately, recent Western scholarship has preferred to utilize a loose and often inaccurate Persian translation of the original Chaghatay done by a certain Ismāʿīl Amīr Khīzī, based on a MS in the National Library of Iran (Kitābkhāna-ʾi Millī-yi Malik), that was included by ʿAlī Asghar Ḥikmat in the introduction to his edition of two medieval Persian translations of ʿAlī Shīr Navāʾī’s *Majālis al-nafāʾis*, rather than either the Uzbek or Turkish transcriptions.²⁶

²² I. Berezin, *Turetskaia khrestomatia*, 3 vols. (Kazan, 1857–76), 1:162–66. Berezin did not state which manuscript he used.

²³ ʿAlī Shīr Navāʾī, *Vaqfiyya* (Baku: Azerb. Gos. Izd., 1926). It was published on the occasion of Navāʾī’s jubilee and the First All-Union Turcological Congress held in Baku. A Russian translation of an excerpt from this edition was done by A. K. Borovkov and incorporated into an article by A. M. Belenitskii, “Istoricheskaia topografiia Gerata XV v.,” in *Alisher Navoi*, ed. Borovkov, 128–200. A possible explanation for its disappearance is that, since it was probably a popular edition, it was withdrawn from general circulation when the Soviet prohibition against printed materials in the Arabic script went into effect in 1929. I have not been successful in locating a copy of this edition. For a full reference to it, see E. D. Svidina, *Alisher Navoi: Bibliografiia* (Tashkent, 1968), 13.

²⁴ Alisher Navoi, *Asarlar*, 15 vols. (Tashkent, 1963–68), 13 (1966): 159–80. The edition, presumably based on MSS from Soviet libraries, was done by Suiima Ganieva.

²⁵ Ağâh Sırrı Levend, *Ali Şir Nevaî*, 4 vols. (Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu Basımevi, 1965–68), 4 (1968): 27–36.

²⁶ ʿAlī Shīr Navāʾī, *Majālis al-nafāʾis*, trans. and expanded by Fakhrī Haravī (entitled *Latāʾif-nāma*) and Muḥammad b. Mubārak al-Qazvīnī (Eng. title page: *The Majālis-un-Nafaʾis, “Galaxy of Poets,” of Mir ‘Ali Shir Nava’i: Two 16th Century Persian Translations*), ed. ʿAlī Asghar Ḥikmat (Teheran,

¹⁹ It is because none of its buildings has survived that the complex was not treated separately in the two most recent works on Timurid architecture, namely, Bernard O’Kane, *Timurid Architecture in Khurasan* (Costa Mesa, Calif.: Mazda Publishers, 1987), and Lisa Golombek and Donald Wilber, *The Timurid Architecture of Iran and Turan*, 2 vols. (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1988). For possible representations of one of the buildings in the complex in the first half of the 19th century, see Terry Allen, *A Catalogue of the Toponyms and Monuments of Timurid Herat* (Cambridge, Mass.: Aga Khan Program for Islamic Architecture, 1981), 92.

²⁰ See, for example, K. M. Munirov and A. Nasirov, *Alisher Navoi asarlarining ŪzSSR Fanlar akademiiasi Sharqshunoslik instituti tūplamidagi qūlēmaları* (Tashkent, 1970), 61–62.

²¹ See for example, S. L. Volin, “Opisanie rukopisei proizvedenii Navoi v leningradskikh sobraniiaxh,” in *Alisher Navoi: Sbornik statei*, ed. A. K. Borovkov (Moscow-Leningrad, 1946), 232–34.

The present study is based on two MSS of the *Vaqfiyya* held in the State Public Library in Leningrad. The first, belonging to the Khanykov collection, is appended to a copy, probably done in Herat and dated 904/1498–99, of an anthology of several of Navāʿī's works.²⁷ Completed two years before Navāʿī's death (in 906/1501), it represents a very good copy that was contemporary with the author. The second, copied in Tabriz in 934/1527–28 by a certain "Chalabī," is also appended to a collection of Navāʿī's works, including *Chihil ḥadīṣ*, the "old" introduction to his *Dīvāns*, and his *Dīvān*.²⁸ Although almost identical with the first, it is in many cases not as accurate and therefore the Khanykov manuscript was used as the control in this study. In addition, both the above-mentioned Uzbek and Turkish transcriptions of the *Vaqfiyya* have been consulted for possible variants.

LOCATION OF THE COMPLEX AND DISPOSITION
OF ITS BUILDINGS

The Bāgh-i Marghanī. ʿAlī Shīr states that, in the year 881/1476–77,²⁹ he was granted a tract of land (*yer*) by Ḥusain Bāyqarā near a location called Kūshk-i Marghanī³⁰ in order to build for himself a personal

1323/1945; repr. ed., 1363/1985), xx–xxv [hereafter MN (Per. trans.)].

²⁷ ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī, *Vaqfiyya*, ms, Leningrad, State Public Library, Khanykov, 55, fols. 111b–118b. For particulars about the manuscript, see Volin, "Opisanie," 231, no. XVI (1) and 232, no. XVII (1).

²⁸ ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī, *Vaqfiyya*, ms, Leningrad, State Public Library, Tur. n. s. 56, fols. 200b–224b [hereafter V (GPB II)]. For a description, see Volin, "Opisanie," 231, no. XVI (2) and 233, no. 3.

²⁹ Note the incorrect year 880 given in the introduction to MN (Per. trans.), xxi. Thus also in Golombek and Wilber, *Timurid Architecture*, 1:64, where Allen's translation of the passage is reproduced.

³⁰ Other possible readings of this toponym (written مرغنی) are Marghnī (thus Levend: Merḡni), Maraghnī, Murghanī, etc. The spelling Mīrghanī found in Muʿin al-Dīn Zamchī Isfīzārī, *Rauzāt al-jannāt fī auṣaf-i madīnat-i Harāt*, ed. Sayyid Muḥammad Kāzīm, 2 vols. (Teheran, 1338–39/1959–60) [hereafter RJ], 2:40, should be seen as a corruption of the original form; for the possible etymology of the word, see n. 44 below. Note that in the introduction to MN (Per. trans.), xxi, it is given incorrectly as Kūshk-i Murghāb!

residence (*sarā*) surrounded by grounds (*ḥavīlī*).³¹ This tract of land he says was located on the northern limits (*ḥadd*) of Herat, at the foot (*etek*) of Gāzurgāh mountain, between its southern side (*ḥadd*) and the city.³² From the direction of Gāzurgāh flowed the Jūy-i nau river (*rūd*) and from the direction of the city, the Injil canal (*su*). The climate of the place was apparently extremely salutary and it was favored by a pleasant breeze.³³ ʿAlī Shīr says that he enclosed 30 *jarībs*³⁴ of this tract with a wall (*dīvār*), within which he built his residence and brought the land under cultivation until, in his words, "I made its orchard-garden (*bāghcha*) beautiful with every sort of [fruit] tree and adorned its meadows (*chaman*) with every sort of herbiage."³⁵ Apparently, others, whom ʿAlī Shīr refers to as "sons of amirs and royal princes," had tried to do the same here in the past, but they had not met with success.³⁶

It is clear from ʿAlī Shīr's account that the Kūshk-i Marghanī was an actual structure. He says that it was a very ancient edifice (*ʿimārat*) located "between the southern and western sides (*ḥadd*) of the grounds' enclosure (*ḥavīlī maḥūṭasi*)."³⁷ Its structure (*binā*) was of stone (*tashdīn*) and its walls of unbaked brick (*khām*

³¹ For the term, *ḥavīlī*, see Chekhovich, *Samarkandskie dokumenty*, 312–13. Note that in the introduction to MN (Per. trans.), xxi, the terms *yer* and *ḥavīlī* are both translated incorrectly as "*bāghcha*."

³² He refers to Herat simply as "the aforementioned populated place" (*maʿmūra-ʿi maḥkūra*).

³³ V (GPB), fol. 115a.

³⁴ The equivalent of approximately 18.5 acres. Allen (*Catalogue*, 198 and 200) calculated this area as 12 acres, but he took the *jarīb* as equal to 1592 sq. m., which was its canonical size in the classical period of Islam; see Walther Hinz, *Islamische Masse und Gewichte* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1955), 65. For a discussion of the size of the *jarīb* in 15th-century Khorasan, see below.

³⁵ V (GPB), fol. 115b. It is obvious from this context that the "*bāghcha*" ʿAlī Shīr mentions does not merit the prominence accorded to it by Allen; see Allen, *Catalogue*, 96 and 200.

³⁶ V (GPB), fols. 115a–115b.

³⁷ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 5–6. Note that in Allen, *Catalogue*, 94, this is incorrectly translated as "in the middle of the south side and to the east (*sic*) of this *baghchah*." But note Masson's caveat about taking at face value references to points of the compass in medieval sources since these often indicated relative location only; M. E. Masson, "K istoricheskoi topografii Gerata XV veka," in *Velikii uzbekskii poet: Sbornik statei*, ed. M. T. Aibek (Tashkent, 1948), 134.

kerpichdin).³⁸ It had been built on two stories (*iki asham*), and although now fallen into ruin, its upper storey (*yuqarighi ashami*) still appears to have been intact.³⁹ ʿAlī Shīr says that he razed it to the ground and in its place built a mosque and a madrasa.⁴⁰

What is extremely interesting is that ʿAlī Shīr refers to this structure as a “monastery-like building” (*binā-yi dair-paivand*) and as a “foundation resembling a church” (*asās-i kalīsā-mānand*).⁴¹ As if to underscore the fact that he was not merely making a fanciful literary allusion, ʿAlī Shīr repeats himself in a versified couplet, in which he says: “In place of that monastery (*dair*) and church (*kalīsā*), a madrasa and mosque were built.”⁴² There can be no doubt that this had formerly been a Christian sanctuary.⁴³ The Nestorian Christian presence in Khorasan, and in Herat in particular, is fairly well documented.⁴⁴ Moreover, there are several

direct references in sources as early as the 10th century to a Christian church to the north of Herat whose location appears to correspond exactly to that of the Kūshk-i Marghanī.⁴⁵ Since the monastic life was an inseparable feature of Nestorian Christianity in Central Asia, the Kūshk would naturally have served a dual purpose, thus explaining ʿAlī Shīr’s statement that it was both a church and a monastery. Furthermore, ʿAlī Shīr’s construction of a mosque on the former site of a Christian church was in keeping with a well-established practice in Central Asia by which Islam sought not only to demonstrate its supremacy over other religions it had been in competition with, but, at the same time, to legitimate itself through the sanctity and prestige that the popular imagination associated with such former shrines.⁴⁶

³⁸ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 6–7.

³⁹ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 7–9.

⁴⁰ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 12–13.

⁴¹ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 12–13.

⁴² V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 13–14. This section is entirely omitted in the introduction to MN (Per. trans.), xxi. Masson was the only scholar ever to have remarked on this fascinating reference (based on Borovkov’s Russian translation); see Masson, “K istoricheskoi topografii,” 122, n. 1.

⁴³ *Dair* (a word of Syriac origin) always denoted a Christian monastery, which was usually named after its patron saint; see “*Dayr*,” in EI (new ed.), 2:194. *Kalīsā* designated equally the cultic place of the Jews, Christians, and pagans; see “*Kanīsa*,” in EI (new ed.), 4:545. ʿAlī Shīr’s use of it in conjunction with *dair*, however, fixes its meaning in this case.

⁴⁴ There was a Nestorian bishop in Herat by the mid-5th century and a metropolitan by the end of the 6th (see V. V. Bartol’d, “O khristianstve v Turkestane v domongol’skii period,” in V. V. Bartol’d, *Sochineniia*, 10 vols. [Moscow, 1963–77], 2.2:275), and the metropolitanate still figures at the beginning of the 14th c. [see Jean Maurice Fiey, “Chrétientés syriaques du Ḥorāsān et du Ségestan,” *Communautés syriaques en Iran et Irak des origines à 1552* (London: Variorum Reprints, 1979), 6:89–92]. In the *Tārīkh-nāma-ʿi Ḥarāt* of Saifī Haravī, Christians are still mentioned in Herat at the beginning of the 14th century; see I. P. Petrushevskii, “Trud Seifī kak istochnik po istorii vostochnogo Khorasana,” *Trudy Iuzhno-turkmenistanskoi arkheologicheskoi kompleksnoi ekspeditsii* (1955), 5:158–59. Petrushevskii considered this as probably the latest mention of a Christian community in Khorasan. In the opinion of Fiey, this community disappeared by the end of the 14th century; see Fiey, “Chrétientés syriaques,” 92. The fact that our Kūshk is described as having been

an ancient edifice would appear to corroborate both scholars’ statements. At the same time, the existence of representations of Christian monasteries in miniature paintings attributed to late Timurid Herat would point to a not too distant memory of them. See, for example, the extremely interesting miniature of a Christian monastery attributed to Herat of the second quarter of the 15th century in E. Akurgal, C. Mango, and R. Ettinghausen, *Treasures of Turkey* (Geneva: Skira, 1966), 231. (For a discussion of this miniature, see *Islamic Art*, 1 [1981], especially the articles by Peter Alford Andrews, “The Turco-Mongol Context of Some Objects Shown in the Istanbul Album Pictures,” 110–20, and Lisa Golombek, “Some Representations of Architecture in the Istanbul Albums,” 130–35. The latter reached the conclusion that the miniature was a pastiche. I am grateful to Lisa Golombek for bringing it to my attention.)

⁴⁵ For example, the Arab geographer, al-Iṣṭakhrī (10th century), mentions a Christian church in Herat that he says was located between the city and a fire temple called Sirishk which was on the mountain of Herat (*ʿalā raʿs al-jabal*), one-half farsang north of Herat on the Balkh road; al-Iṣṭakhrī, *Kitāb masālik al-mamālik*, ed. M. J. de Goeje, 2nd ed. (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1927), 265. He also locates it north of the Injil when he states that the only water between the church and the city was “the river of the city” (*nahr al-madīna*), i.e., the Injil canal, which could be crossed by means of a bridge at the city gate; al-Iṣṭakhrī, *Masālik al-mamālik*, 265. This same location is mentioned by Qazvīnī (mid-14th century), who, however, already speaks of the church in the past tense; Ḥamdullāh Mustaufī al-Qazvīnī, *Nuzhat al-qulūb*, ed. G. Le Strange (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1915), 152.

⁴⁶ For examples of mosques built on the sites of former Christian churches, see Bartol’d, *Sochineniia*, 2.2:275 (for Bukhara) and 287 (for Talas [Taraz]). Zeki Velidi Togan, in

In the *Khulāṣat al-akhbār*, Khvāndamīr refers to the enclosed grounds that ʿAlī Shīr constructed as Bāgh-i Marghanī.⁴⁷ Since this was obviously not a name that ʿAlī Shīr had chosen himself, what had most probably occurred was that the Kūshk-i Marghanī, which since ancient times must have stood at the centre of a Christian community, gave its name to the whole area surrounding it, thus recalling the way in which the Kūshk-i

his article, "Herat," in *Islām ansiklopedisi* (Istanbul, 1940-) [hereafter *ĪA*], 5:434, connected the name of the Kūshk-i Marghanī with an ʿIzz al-Dīn ʿUmar Marghānī (d. 743/1342) who had been in Ilkhanid service. This was also the opinion of Allen, *Catalogue*, 200, who also suggested that he may have been the builder of the Kūshk. However, in view of the fact that we are dealing with a Nestorian Christian site of long standing, and given the obscure origin and many variant readings of this toponym, it is possible that it derives from the name of the patron saint after which the monastery-church complex had originally been named, this usually being prefaced by the Syriac word *mār*, meaning "saint." Another possible etymology for the word is from the old Persian (?) word *marzghan* (مرزغن), which means "cemetery" (see S. I. Baevskii, "Srednevekove slovari (*farkhangī*)—istochnik po istorii kul'tury Irana," in *Ocherki istorii kul'tury srednevekovogo Irana*, ed. O. F. Akimushkin and Z. N. Vorozheikina [Moscow, 1984], 222) and which would have referred to the ancient burial ground whose traces might still have existed at the former site of the Christian church cum monastery. Another possibility is that the word derives from the name of the Nestorian Christian tribe, Mārgit/Mākrit (sg. Mārgān) that lived in Uighuristan in the Mongol period, but that, according to Rashīd al-Dīn, was neither Mongol nor Uighur. These Mākrit/Mākrin (also called Qayachi or "rock climbers") were still mentioned at the end of the 14th century in connection with Tīmūr's campaigns in Georgia. They were identified as the Christian tribe of the Kerait by Paul Pelliot, *Recherches sur les chrétiens d'Asie Centrale et d'Extrême-Orient* (Paris, 1973), 30–33. Although this etymology may seem somewhat far-fetched, it was suggested by similar toponyms in the immediate vicinity of the Kūshk bearing the names of Turko-Mongol tribes, such as: Kūshk-i Qarlugh (attested in Saifī Haravī, *Tārīkh-nāma-ʿi Harāt*, ed. Muḥammad Zubair al-Ṣiddīqī [Calcutta, 1944], 248) and the Darvāza-ʿi Qipchāq, the name of the eastern gate of the city on the north side (see Allen, *Catalogue*, 38).

⁴⁷ KhA, 25. He corroborates the fact that this *bāgh* was ʿAlī Shīr's grounds by saying that ʿAlī Shīr brought it to flourishing condition. Note that the term *bāgh* denoted an enclosed cultivated area bearing permanent cultures (fruit trees, vineyards, etc.); see "*Bāḡ*," in *Encyclopaedia Iranica* (London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1982-), 3:393.

Mughān suburb of Samanid Bukhara got its name.⁴⁸ The name for the area then came to be popularly applied to the enclosed grounds which ʿAlī Shīr constructed for himself here, without, however, becoming an actual place name.⁴⁹

ʿAlī Shīr's residence. Khvāndamīr speaks of the Bāgh-i Marghanī as containing several buildings (*imārāt*) which he refers to as "palaces" (*quṣūr*).⁵⁰ Although ʿAlī Shīr gives no details about the residence he built on his enclosed grounds, Bābur, who called it "Unsiyya," referred to it as consisting of several houses.⁵¹

Qudsiyya mosque. Since, for the reasons mentioned above, ʿAlī Shīr undoubtedly built his mosque on the exact former site of the Kūshk-i Marghanī which had been located in the southwest corner of the Bāgh's enclosure, this is where it must have been located. The mosque's location within the Bāgh's enclosure is confirmed by Khvāndamīr, who states that it was built inside (*dar darūn*) the Bāgh-i Marghanī.⁵² Further details about its location are provided by Khvāndamīr, who says that it was opposite (*muḥāzī*) ʿAlī Shīr's residence,⁵³ and by ʿAlī Shīr himself who says that it was to the west of the madrasa.⁵⁴ ʿAlī Shīr also notes that the mosque's *qibla* was on its western side.⁵⁵

Although ʿAlī Shīr does not state so explicitly in the *Vaqfiyya*, other sources make it clear that this was a congregational mosque (*masjid-i jāmiʿ*). Bābur calls it a *masjid-i jāmiʿ*,⁵⁶ and in his *Majālis al-nafāʿis*, ʿAlī Shīr refers to it as the "Qudsiyya congregational

⁴⁸ For this see W. Barthold [V. V. Bartol'd], *Turkestan down to the Mongol Invasion*, 4th ed. ([Cambridge]: E. J. W. Gibb Memorial Trust, 1977), 108.

⁴⁹ This contention seems to be borne out by the fact that Kūshk-i Marghanī does not appear at all in Ḥāfīz-i Abrū's geographical work; see Dorothea Krawulsky, ed. and trans., *Ḥorāsān zur Timuridenzeit nach dem Tārīh-e Ḥāfez-e Abrū (verf. 817–823 h.)*, Beihefte zum Tübinger Atlas des Vorderen Orients, Reihe B, Nr. 46/1–2, 2 vols. (Wiesbaden: Ludwig Reichert Verlag, 1982–84).

⁵⁰ KhA, 26.

⁵¹ *ʿAlīshīr Begning olturur oylari*; BN, fol. 191b.

⁵² Ghiyāṣ al-Dīn Khvāndamīr, *Makārim al-akhlāq*, fac. ed. T. Gandjei ([Cambridge:] Trustees of the "E. J. W. Gibb Memorial," 1979) [hereafter MA], fol. 147v.

⁵³ KhA, 18.

⁵⁴ Lit., "as one enters the madrasa, the mosque is on its western side"; V (GPB), fol. 115b, l. 14.

⁵⁵ V (GPB), fol. 115b, l. 14.

⁵⁶ BN, fol. 191b.

mosque.”⁵⁷ In the *Khulāṣat al-akhbār*, Khvāndamīr states that a *masjid-i jāmiʿ*, which he describes as having two minarets, one on the left and the other on the right side, was located opposite (*muḥāzī*) ʿAlī Shīr’s residence (*manzil*).⁵⁸ However, in the *Makārim al-akhlāq*, he introduces some confusion into the matter when, after describing a mosque (which he simply calls *masjid*) that he says ʿAlī Shīr built inside (*dar darūn*) the Bāgh-i Marghanī,⁵⁹ he says ʿAlī Shīr built another (which he calls *masjid-i jāmiʿ*) opposite (*dar muḥāzī*) the Bāgh-i Marghanī.⁶⁰ This appears, however, to have been one and the same building.

Ikhhlāṣiyya madrasa. As for the location of the madrasa, ʿAlī Shīr says only that the Injil canal (*arigh*) flowed along its southern exterior (*junūbī ḥaddining tashidin*).⁶¹ Khvāndamīr corroborates this by saying that it was located “on the bank” (*dar kinār*) of the Injil.⁶² ʿAlī Shīr’s statements above would seem to indicate that the madrasa was also within the Bāgh’s enclosure. In the main hall (*tur*) of the madrasa, which was on its northern side (*ḥadd*), there was a domed chamber (*gunbad*), which ʿAlī Shīr says was called “Dār al-ḥuffāz” (College of Koran Reciters).⁶³ Khvāndamīr gives an indication of the location of the madrasa relative to the mosque when he says that the Dār al-ḥuffāz was to the north of it.⁶⁴ Finally, ʿAlī Shīr confirms that the name of the madrasa was indeed Ikhhlāṣiyya when he says that he gave it this name because he built it “out of pure sincerity” (*khulūṣ-i ikhlāṣdin*).⁶⁵

Khalāṣiyya khanaqah. According to the *Vaqfiyya*, the khanaqah was located facing (*muqābala*) the Ikhhlāṣiyya madrasa.⁶⁶ Khvāndamīr too says that it was built opposite (*dar muḥāzī*) the madrasa.⁶⁷ ʿAlī Shīr says that it was to the south of the public thoroughfare (*shāriʿ-i ʿāmm*)⁶⁸ that ran along the southern bank of the Injil

canal,⁶⁹ all the way to the Gauhar Shād madrasa.⁷⁰ He notes that Sultan Husain Bāyqarā’s madrasa, which he says was called “Ni^cmatābād,” was also located along this thoroughfare.⁷¹ Thus, the Injil canal flowed between the madrasa and khanaqah.⁷² The two, however, formed an ensemble. This fact is confirmed by ʿAlī Shīr’s requirement that the area between the two buildings that had been paved over with stones be regularly maintained to allow people to pass freely between them.⁷³ Since the khanaqah was located along a public thoroughfare and was, generally speaking, more of a public building than the madrasa, the enclosure of ʿAlī Shīr’s grounds would probably not have encompassed it, the Injil canal having formed the natural southern boundary of the Bāgh-i Marghanī.

In the main hall (*tur*) of the khanaqah, which was on its southern side (*taraf*), there was a domed chamber (*gunbad*).⁷⁴ ʿAlī Shīr says that he named the khanaqah “Khalāṣiyya” because it was a building free of ostentation and pretense, that freed (*khalāṣ berdi*) the mind from its troubles.⁷⁵ ʿAlī Shīr’s unequivocal statement would seem to resolve the confusion about which of the buildings was called Ikhhlāṣiyya and which Khalāṣiyya.⁷⁶ Nonetheless, the name Ikhhlāṣiyya is often applied to both. This can be explained by the fact that the madrasa was the more prestigious and important of the two and, since it was linked to the khanaqah over the Injil, its name was frequently applied to the whole complex.⁷⁷

Apparently, the khanaqah and ʿAlī Shīr’s mosque were not very close to each other. ʿAlī Shīr says that the suburb (*maḥalla*)⁷⁸ around the khanaqah had been built up during Husain Bāyqarā’s rule and had become quite populous.⁷⁹ Because there was “a bit of a

⁵⁷ ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī [Alisher Navoi], *Majālis al-nafāʿis* [*Mazholisun nafaʿis*], ed. S. Ganieva (Tashkent, 1961) [hereafter MN], 154.

⁵⁸ KhA, 18.

⁵⁹ MA, fol. 147v.

⁶⁰ *Va aizan dar muḥāzī-yi Bāgh-i Marghanī masjid-i jāmiʿī . . . sākhṭa and*; MA, fol. 148r.

⁶¹ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 20–21.

⁶² MA, fol. 132v.

⁶³ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 15–18.

⁶⁴ KhA, 18.

⁶⁵ V (GPB), fol. 115b, l. 20.

⁶⁶ V (GPB), fol. 115b, l. 27–fol. 116a, l. 1.

⁶⁷ MA, fol. 145v.

⁶⁸ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 1.

⁶⁹ *Ol arighning junūbī ḥaddi kim qiraghi bolghay shāriʿ-i ʿāmm dur*; V (GPB), fol. 115b, l. 21.

⁷⁰ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 26–27.

⁷¹ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 25–26. Note that this was not a separate building, as suggested by Allen, *Catalogue*, 160, #540.

⁷² *Dar miyān-i ānhā*; KhA, 19.

⁷³ *Madrasa va khānaqāh arasida kim tash salib durlar*; V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 24–25.

⁷⁴ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 3.

⁷⁵ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 8.

⁷⁶ As, for example, in BN, fol. 191b.

⁷⁷ Thus even in MN, 154, although not in the *Vaqfiyya* itself.

⁷⁸ For the term *maḥalla*, see R. G. Mukminova, “Nekotorye dannye o vakufnoi gramote v pol’zu dvukh medrese Mukhammed Sheibani-khana,” *Izvestiia Akademii nauk Uzbekskoi SSR* (Seriia obshchestvennykh nauk) (1957), 3:20.

⁷⁹ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 3.

distance" (*juzvī masāfatī*) between the congregation (*jamā'at*) living there and the congregational mosques (note 'Alī Shīr's use of the plural, by which he must have meant the chief congregational mosque of the city, his own, and the Gauhar Shād mosque), he says that people used the pretext of cold in winter and heat in summer not to go to mosque at all.⁸⁰

The hospital and bath. Of the hospital and bath that Bābur says were called Shifā'iyya and Ṣafā'iyya respectively, 'Alī Shīr says nothing in the *Vaqfiyya*. From Khvādamīr, however, we know that the hospital was located west of the madrasa⁸¹ and south of 'Alī Shīr's mosque.⁸² The fact that he mentions it as being "close to the madrasa" would seem to indicate that it was located north of the Injil.⁸³ We also know that in the middle of the hospital there was a large pool (*hauz*).⁸⁴

It is difficult to locate the Ikhlaṣiyya complex precisely, in view of the inadequate information contained both in the *Vaqfiyya* and in the other sources of the period. In his reconstruction of the historical topography of late Timurid Herat, Allen located the entire complex north of the Injil canal, and separate from the Bāgh-i Marghanī.⁸⁵ However, according to 'Alī Shīr's *Vaqfiyya*, although the mosque, madrasa, and 'Alī Shīr's private residence were indeed located north of the Injil, they were all within the enclosure of 'Alī Shīr's grounds—the so-called Bāgh-i Marghanī—while the khanaqah was located south of the Injil and linked to the madrasa over it. Basing himself on the location of the "waterbox (*naṭara*) of Mirghānī," Allen further located the complex next to Khiyābān and the madrasa of Ḥusain Bāyqarā.⁸⁶ Although a very vague reference

to Kūshk-i Marghanī is made by the early Timurid historian, Ḥāfiẓ-i Abrū, who calls it the place (*mauzi'*) or near the place where "the water of the Injil enters the city [of Herat],"⁸⁷ the complex cannot be located simply on this basis alone, since, by Ḥāfiẓ-i Abrū's time, the term Marghanī probably no longer referred to a specific location, but to the whole vicinity around the ancient Kūshk structure. Moreover, the location of the madrasa and khanaqah close to the madrasa of Sultan Ḥusain, and therefore also to the Gauhar Shād complex, would seem to be ruled out by 'Alī Shīr's statement that the khanaqah was some distance from any cathedral mosques, as well as by the fact that he does not even mention Khiyābān in the *Vaqfiyya*. Therefore, the chief buildings of the Ikhlaṣiyya complex—the madrasa and khanaqah—must have been located further east along the Injil than indicated by Allen, and partly to the south of it.⁸⁸ As for the disposition of the other buildings, their locations are indicated only in relative terms and therefore cannot be established precisely.⁸⁹

PERSONNEL AND ACTIVITIES OF THE COMPLEX

In accordance with the rules for the establishment of a legal *vaqf*, the endower had the right to stipulate the activities that the income from his endowment would

⁸⁷ [Ḥāfiẓ-i Abrū], *Cinq opuscules de Ḥāfiẓ-i Abrū concernant l'histoire de l'Iran au temps de Tamerlan*, ed. Felix Tauer (Prague, 1959), 64. Almost the exact same passage is found in Sharaf al-Dīn Yazdī, who calls it a "crossing" (*mamarr*); see Sharaf al-Dīn 'Alī Yazdī [Sharafuddin Ali Iazdii], *Zafar-nāma [Zafornoma]*, ed. A. Urumbaev (Tashkent, 1972), fol. 168a.

⁸⁸ I would argue for the location given by Togan on his map entitled "Timurlar devrindeki Büyük Herat" in "Herat," in *IA*, 5:429–42, although it ought to be noted that Togan did not say how he arrived at it.

⁸⁹ The precision with which Togan drew up the plan of what he calls "'Alī Shīr's quarter" ("Herat," in *IA*, 5:429–42), is not supported by the information contained in the *Vaqfiyya*, while some buildings (such as the "Ġalūrḥāna," for example) are not even mentioned in it. Although Togan claimed to have based his plan (dated 1923) on 'Alī Shīr's *Vaqfiyya* ("*bu emīrin vakfiyesinde*," 434) and on *vaqf* documents ("*vakfiyelere göre*" in the plan's title; "*vakıf vesikalarına dayanarak*," 442), he does not provide the names or locations of the manuscripts or documents he used. Moreover, his reference to documents in the plural is extremely problematic, for it suggests that he was also working from those original (Persian) *vaqf* documents that 'Alī Shīr mentioned in the *Vaqfiyya* but that have long since disappeared.

⁸⁰ V (GPB), vol. 116a, ll. 4–6.

⁸¹ MA, fol. 133r.

⁸² KhA, 19.

⁸³ KhA, 19.

⁸⁴ KhA, 19.

⁸⁵ Allen, *Catalogue*, 94–97 and 200; see also map 2, #413 and #636. Allen based himself on the inaccurate and incomplete Persian translation of the crucial relevant passage of the *Vaqfiyya* contained in the introduction to MN (Per. trans.), xxi, in which the mistranslation of the term *havīlī* ("grounds") as "*bāghcha*" became the cause of much confusion. See Allen, *Catalogue*, 94 and 200, where the "*bāghcha*" he refers to and which he translates as a "small garden" was actually the enclosed grounds on which the complex was built, these being referred to in the sources as Bāgh-i Marghanī.

⁸⁶ See Allen, *Catalogue*, 23 and map 1, #43. Following Allen, thus also Golombek and Wilber, *Timurid Architecture*, I:64. Khiyābān was the broad avenue that ran north from the city; see Allen, *Catalogue*, 46.

support, to fix the salaries and stipends of its personnel, and to set down whatever conditions (*sharā'it*) he deemed necessary or appropriate for its maintenance and continued existence.

Alī Shīr stipulated that a "sweet-voiced" *imām* (leader in prayer) and a "mellifluous-sounding" Koran reader (*muqrī*) should be appointed to his mosque in order to perform the five daily prayers with the people of the quarter and to pray for the sultan.⁹⁰ Both posts appear to have been filled by one and the same person since Khvāndamīr says that Alī Shīr appointed Khvāja Ḥāfiẓ Muḥammad Sulṭānshāh, whom he calls the best Koran reader (*qārī*)⁹¹ of the day, to be the *imām* of the mosque.⁹¹ Also, in the *Majālis al-naḥā'is*, Alī Shīr states that a Ḥāfiẓ Jalāl al-Dīn Maḥmūd was both the *khaṭīb* (preacher) and *imām* of his mosque.⁹²

As for the madrasa, two pious religious scholars (*ālīm*), one of whom was to lecture on Islamic jurisprudence (*fiqh*) and the other on the traditions of the Prophet (*hadīth*), were to be appointed as professors (*mudarris*) to lecture in its eastern and western estrades (*ṣuffa*).⁹³ Since he exerted considerable influence in the appointment of professors to other madrasas in Herat,⁹⁴ Alī Shīr undoubtedly had great control over teaching appointments at his own madrasa, particularly since he had the right to do so as an endower (*vāqif*).⁹⁵ Despite the fact that Alī Shīr's endowment only provided for two professors to teach in his madrasa, in the *Makārim al-akhlāq*, Khvāndamīr noted that by 906/1501 (the year of Alī Shīr's death), there were four scholars teaching here: Amīr Burhān al-Dīn Atā'ullāh Nīshāpūrī,⁹⁶ Qāẓī Ikhtiyār al-Dīn Ḥasan Turbatī,⁹⁷ Amīr Murtāz,⁹⁸ and Maulānā Faṣīḥ al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Nizāmī.⁹⁹

Alī Shīr further indicated that there were to be two study circles (*ḥalqa*) of eleven students each, thus making the total number of students studying at the

madrasa who were supported by the endowment twenty-two.¹⁰⁰ One of the madrasa's more famous students was the composer of enigmas, Maulānā Mīr Ḥusain Mu'ammā'ī, who lived here for several years and was later buried in the madrasa's domed chamber (i.e., Dār al-ḥuffāz).¹⁰¹

Every day, Koran reciters (*ḥāfiẓ*), of whom six were to be appointed,¹⁰² were to read a section (*sipāra*—lit., a thirtieth part) of the Koran in the Dār al-ḥuffāz of the madrasa for the sake of the soul of the Prophet, so that, by the end of the month, they could complete the reading of the entire Koran with a prayer for Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā.¹⁰³

The khanaqah was a charitable institution that housed Sufi dervishes headed by a shaiḥ who, according to the *Majālis al-naḥā'is*, was the same Ḥāfiẓ Jalāl al-Dīn Maḥmūd who fulfilled the functions of *imām-khaṭīb* in Alī Shīr's mosque.¹⁰⁴ Its primary function was that of a "soup kitchen" which distributed food to the poor on a daily basis. Khvāndamīr says that it served more than a 1000 people every day.¹⁰⁵ To help with the cooking and distribution of food and with maintenance, Alī Shīr stipulated that the khanaqah was to have a cook (*ṭabbākh*),¹⁰⁶ a server (*ṭabaqchī*),¹⁰⁷ a concierge (*farrāsh*) and two servants (*khādīm*).¹⁰⁸ The food was to be distributed in accordance with the following instructions,¹⁰⁹ which Alī Shīr lists under the heading, "rations" (*ravātib*):¹¹⁰

Every night during the month of the Fast:¹¹¹ 15 *batman* of wheat, 5 *batman* of rice pudding (*palūda*), 30 platters of grape or raisin extract (*dūshāb, mavīzāb*), and whatever else is necessary.

¹⁰⁰ V (GPB), fol. 115b, l. 19 and fol. 117b, ll. 22–23. V (GPB II) gives the number as twelve—fol. 215b, although later it gives eleven—fol. 222a. Twenty-two appears to have been the standard number of students in such institutions; see "Madrasa," in EI (new ed.), 5:1128.

¹⁰¹ HS, 4:343.

¹⁰² V (GPB), fol. 117b, l. 25.

¹⁰³ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 16–18.

¹⁰⁴ MN, 154; note that in the text the khanaqah is referred to as *Ikhlāṣiyya*!

¹⁰⁵ MA, fol. 145v.

¹⁰⁶ V (GPB), fol. 117b, l. 27.

¹⁰⁷ V (GPB), fol. 118a, l. 1.

¹⁰⁸ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 1–2.

¹⁰⁹ V (GPB), fol. 116a, ll. 1–2.

¹¹⁰ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 5–14.

¹¹¹ I.e., Ramaḍān, the 9th month of the Muslim calendar, during which the fast is observed from dawn until nightfall, after which it is permissible to eat.

⁹⁰ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 14–15.

⁹¹ MA, fol. 147v.

⁹² MN, 154.

⁹³ V (GPB), fol. 115b, ll. 18–19.

⁹⁴ For an example of a professor who was dismissed from Ḥusain Bāyqarā's madrasa because he fell out of favor with Alī Shīr, see HS, 4:347; for his consultation with religious scholars about an appointment to the Ghīyāsiyya madrasa, see HS, 4:343.

⁹⁵ See "Madrasa," in EI (new ed.), 5:1128.

⁹⁶ For him, see HS, 4:353.

⁹⁷ For him, see HS, 4:355–56.

⁹⁸ For him, see HS, 4:349.

⁹⁹ MA, fols. 132v–133r. For Faṣīḥ al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Nizāmī, see HS, 4:352–53.

On the Feast of ʿĪd:¹¹² 100 *batman* of bread and 50 *batman* of sweets (*ḥalvā*).

On the first day of the Feast of Qurbān:¹¹³ One cow and 5 sheep will be slaughtered and distributed to the dervishes, the poor and the other inhabitants of the madrasa and khanaqah. On the second day: *Ḥalīm* (= kind of dish) will be made with 20 *batman* of meat and 20 *batman* of wheat and distributed together with 50 *batman* of bread. Soup (*āsh*) will be cooked with whatever is necessary and distributed together with 50 *batman* of bread.¹¹⁴

On the 12th of the month of Rabīʿ al-awwal, on which the Koran is read in its entirety (*khatm*) [to commemorate the anniversary of the birth of the Prophet]: Soup will be prepared with 5 sheep and whatever else is necessary and distributed together with 50 *batman* of bread and 20 *batman* of sweets.

At the commencement of the academic year (Istiftāh gūni) on the 15th of the month of Rajab:¹¹⁵ 20 *batman* of sweets and 50 *batman* of bread.

On the Night of Barāt, which falls on the eve of the 15th of Shaʿbān:¹¹⁶ 30 *batman* of *chalpak* (= kind of cake fried in oil and butter) and 20 *batman* of sweets.

Every day during the four winter months, Sagittarius, Capricorn, Aquarius and Pisces: 100 [loaves] of bread,

being [the equivalent of] roughly 20 *batman* of wheat.¹¹⁷ 20 *batman* of wheat and 3 *tangas*' worth of meat are to be readied for *ḥalīm*. If meat is unavailable, soup made from sheep's tail (*jijighligh āsh*) is to be cooked and given to the poor. During the [other] eight months: 20 *batman* of bread will be distributed every day to the poor.

Although Khvāndamīr states that the khanaqah annually distributed more than 2000 articles of clothing to "the deserving,"¹¹⁸ the *Vaqfiyya* made provision for the trustee to purchase only about 600 per year: 100 fur-lined garments (*pūstīn*), 100 woollen cloaks (*kepenek*), 100 sheep-skin caps (*būrk*), 100 pairs of shoes, 100 shirts and 100 pairs of breeches.¹¹⁹ The fact that these were to be distributed in consultation with the two professors, during the appropriate season of the year, to "the deserving," according to individual merit, would seem to indicate that they were destined for the students of the madrasa and dervishes of the khanaqah, rather than for the needy at large, although the latter possibility cannot be ruled out.¹²⁰

ʿAlī Shīr also indicated that a preacher (*khaṭīb*), Koran reader (*muqrī*), and an *imām* were to be appointed to the khanaqah in order to enable the people of the suburb, who, in his words, were prepared to make "every conceivable excuse" not to make the trip to the congregational mosques for Friday prayer, to perform their prayers in the khanaqah and its domed chamber.

Apparently the khanaqah also had an educational function, for in the *Makārim al-akhlāq*, Khvāndamīr states that three professors also taught in it: Amīr Jamāl al-Dīn ʿAtāʾullāh Aṣīlī,¹²¹ Amīr Ṣadr al-Dīn Ibrāhīm Mashhadī,¹²² and Khvāja ʿImād al-Dīn ʿAbd al-ʿAzīz Abharī.¹²³ Khvāndamīr probably overstates his case when he says that "many thousands" of people came to the Ikhlaṣiyya madrasa and its supporting khanaqah from all parts of the world since their founding, became learned (*dānishmand*) "in a short time"

¹¹² I.e., ʿĪd al-Fiṭr, which marks the end of the fast of Ramaḍān and is celebrated on the 1st of the month of Shawwāl.

¹¹³ I.e., the Feast of the Sacrifice, which is celebrated on the 10th of the month of Dhū ʿl-Hijja.

¹¹⁴ In V (GPB II) alone (fol. 222b) this last sentence reads: "On the day of ʿĀshūr (i.e., the tenth of the month of Muḥarram, the traditional Shiʿite day of mourning for the family of ʿAlī): Soup (*āsh*) will be cooked with 40 *batman* of meat and whatever is necessary and served with 50 *batman* of bread." This may be explained by the fact that the manuscript was copied in Safavid Tabriz, thus under Shiʿite influence. But note that it was also observed in 16th-century Samarkand; see R. G. Mukminova, *K istorii agrarnykh otnoshenii v Uzbekistane xvi v. po materialam "Vakf-name"* (Tashkent, 1966), 309.

¹¹⁵ *Navoi asarlari lugati* (Tashkent, 1972), 284. See also ʿAlī Akbar Dihkhudā, *Lughat-nāma*, (Teheran, 1946-69), fasc. 10:2178, s. v. *rūz-i istiftāh*: "The 15th of Rajab on which the gates of heaven or of the Kaʿba are opened."

¹¹⁶ The night on which the fate of all living Muslims is believed to be decided for the following year.

¹¹⁷ From this statement it may be concluded that a loaf of bread in Timurid Herat weighed approximately 0.2 *mann* (i.e., about 0.6 kg). For the Herati *mann*, see below.

¹¹⁸ MA, fol. 145v.

¹¹⁹ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 14-15.

¹²⁰ *Mustahiqqlarğa har qayisigha istihqāqigha görä*; V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 15-16.

¹²¹ For him, see HS, 4:358-59.

¹²² For him, see HS, 4:352.

¹²³ MA, fol. 133r. For Khvāja ʿImād al-Dīn, see HS, 4:349. Others who taught here at various times were Maulānā Burhān al-Dīn ʿAtāʾullāh al-Rāzī (HS, 4:341) and Maulānā Khalīlullāh (HS, 4:343).

and then returned home.¹²⁴ Since ʿAlī Shīr’s endowment provided full support only for twenty-two students, they must have studied here at their own expense, probably being housed in the khanaqah.¹²⁵ As for the students from the Herat region who had studied in both institutions, Khvāndamīr says that many of these went on to become professors themselves.¹²⁶

Although ʿAlī Shīr does not mention the activities of the hospital, which was one of several in Herat,¹²⁷ from Khvāndamīr we know that one of the doctors who worked here was the famous Maulānā Nizām al-Dīn ʿAbd al-Ḥayy al-Ṭabīb.¹²⁸ We also know that it was a teaching hospital, for Khvāndamīr reports that a Maulānā Ghiyās al-Dīn Muḥammad b. Maulānā Jalāl al-Dīn taught medical texts in it (*kutub-i ṭibbiyya*).¹²⁹

TRUSTEE OF THE FOUNDATION

The entire foundation was to be managed by a trustee (*mutavallī*), who was to be aided by a financial officer (*mushrif*) and a chief intendant (*ṣāhib-jamʿ*).¹³⁰ The trustee was also required to hire two “sturdy aides” (*ābādān naukar*) to help him in the management of the agriculture of the region.¹³¹ Although ʿAlī Shīr says he appointed a trustee himself, he does not actually name him in the *Vaqfiyya*.¹³² The fact that other sources of the period also do not mention by name anyone who held this responsible (and lucrative) post would seem to point to ʿAlī Shīr’s remaining the trustee himself, something which, as already mentioned, was not only admissible under Hanafite law, but also widely practiced at the time.¹³³

This hypothesis appears to be confirmed by the fact that ʿAlī Shīr did not designate the *vaqf* as hereditary in the family of the trustee. The *vaqf-i ahlī* was the most widespread form of *vaqf* in the Timurid period,¹³⁴ and had ʿAlī Shīr designated someone else as trustee,

he probably would also have indicated that the post of *mutavallī* was to remain in the latter’s family, as he did on other similar occasions.¹³⁵ Naturally, if he assumed the post himself, he would not have said anything about descendants, since he had none. Another point which seems to underscore his remaining the trustee was that the complex was widely recognized as being intimately connected with him, the Ikhlašīyya often being referred to simply as “ʿAlī Shīr’s madrasa,” and the Khalāshīyya as his “personal (*khāṣṣa*) khanaqah.”¹³⁶

SALARIES AND STIPENDS OF PERSONNEL

The salaries and stipends (*vazīfa*) of the personnel connected with the pious foundation were paid out in both cash and kind. The highest paid was the trustee (*mutavallī*) who annually received 3000 *altins* in cash and 30 loads (*yük*) of grain (*āshligh*) in kind. He was to keep 4/6ths of this (i.e., 2000 *altins* and 20 *yüks*) for himself and give the remaining 2/6ths to his two aides (*naukar*), each of whom thus received 500 *altins* and 5 *yüks*.¹³⁷ Both the financial officer (*mushrif*) and the intendant (*ṣāhib-jamʿ*) were to receive 500 *altins* and 5 loads of grain annually.¹³⁸

After the trustee, the next highest paid were the two professors of the madrasa who had an annual salary of 1200 *altins* in cash and 24 loads of grain, one-third of which was to be barley and two-thirds wheat.¹³⁹ As for the twenty-two students studying at the madrasa, the six upperclassmen each received 24 *altins* in cash per month and 5 loads of wheat per year; the eight intermediate ones received 16 *altins* per month and 4 loads of wheat per year; while the eight lowerclassmen received 12 *altins* per month and 3 loads of grain per year.¹⁴⁰ ʿAlī Shīr required the stipendiaries (he refers to them as *mavālī*) to reside in the madrasa. If they lived elsewhere and were not present during the hours of instruction, they were to receive only half the fixed stipend.¹⁴¹

¹²⁴ KhA, 19.

¹²⁵ As suggested by Masson, “K istoricheskoi topografii,” 136.

¹²⁶ KhA, 19. Khvāndamīr refers to the Herat region as “*in balad*.”

¹²⁷ See Masson, “K istoricheskoi topografii,” 132–33.

¹²⁸ MA, fol. 133r. For him see HS, 4:342.

¹²⁹ MA, fol. 133r; also KhA, 50, where he calls them the “standard medical texts” (*kutub-i mutadāvila-i ṭibbiyya*).

¹³⁰ V (GPB), fol. 118a, l. 4.

¹³¹ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 2–3.

¹³² *Bir kishi . . . kim üz qibalimdin mutavallī qilib erdim qoydum*; V (GPB), fol. 118b, l. 3.

¹³³ V (GPB), fol. 118a, l. 2.

¹³⁴ Subtelny, “Socioeconomic Bases,” 482–83.

¹³⁵ As in the case of the *vaqf* he established at the shrine of Abū’l-Valīd at Āzādān for which he designated the vazir, Nizām al-Mulk Khvāfī, and his descendants as the trustees; see Fikrī Saljūqī, ed., *Risāla-i mazārāt-i Harāt*, 3 pts. in 1 vol. (Kabul, 1967), pt. 3 (*Ta’līqāt*): 134.

¹³⁶ See, for example, HS, 4:341.

¹³⁷ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 3–4. For *altin* and *yük*, see below.

¹³⁸ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 4–5.

¹³⁹ V (GPB), fol. 117b, l. 22.

¹⁴⁰ V (GPB), fol. 117b, ll. 23–25. V (GPB II) gives the figure of 10 *altins* for a lowerclassman; fol. 222a.

¹⁴¹ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 19–20.

Also among those receiving the highest salaries was the shaikh, or superior of the Sufi dervishes living in the khanaqah. He received 1000 *altins* annually paid out in two equal installments and 10 loads of grain.¹⁴²

The best of the six Koran reciters (*hāfiẓ*) annually received 500 *altins* in cash paid out in two installments and 15 loads of grain. The other five each received 180 *altins* cash and 4 loads of wheat annually.¹⁴³ The popular preacher (*vāʿiẓ*), by whom ʿAlī Shīr must have meant the *imām* or the *khaṭīb* of the khanaqah (which it will be recalled served as the place of Friday prayer for the suburb), received 500 *altins* annually and 10 loads of wheat.¹⁴⁴ The *imām-khaṭīb* of ʿAlī Shīr's congregational mosque, who also taught the primary school (*maktab*), received an annual salary of 500 *altins* and 10 loads of wheat as well.¹⁴⁵

Next in order of size of salary was the cook of the khanaqah who annually received 280 *altins* in cash and 5 loads of wheat.¹⁴⁶ The lowest paid were the server (*ṭabaqchī*), concierge (*farrāsh*), two servants (*khādīm*), and Koran reader (*muqrī*) of the khanaqah, each of whom received 200 *altins* in cash and 5 loads of wheat annually.¹⁴⁷

ʿAlī Shīr expected the personnel of his complex to conform to high standards of moral conduct. He therefore indicated that if either a professor, student, trustee, shaikh, Koran reciter, or any other employee of the madrasa or khanaqah committed an illegal (*nāmashrūʿ*) act, he was to be punished in accordance with the prescriptions of the Shariʿa up to two infractions of the law, and after the third time, he was to be dismissed and replaced.¹⁴⁸

PROVISIONS FOR MAINTENANCE

The trustee was to spend 400 *altins* every year on furnishings, such as felt rugs, reed mats and lighting, for the khanaqah and its domed chamber (*gunbad*), the madrasa, mosque, and Dār al-ḥuffāz.¹⁴⁹ The trustee was also responsible for providing the khanaqah and its kitchen with everything it required in the way of

¹⁴² V (GPB), fol. 117b, l. 26.

¹⁴³ V (GPB), fol. 117b, ll. 25–26.

¹⁴⁴ V (GPB), fol. 117b, ll. 26–27.

¹⁴⁵ V (GPB II), fol. 222a only. In the Uzbek edition, the salary figure is given as 200 *altins*; Alisher Navoi, *Asarlar*, 13:178.

¹⁴⁶ V (GPB), fol. 117b, l. 27–fol. 118a, l. 1.

¹⁴⁷ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 1–2 and fol. 117b, l. 27.

¹⁴⁸ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 20–23.

¹⁴⁹ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 16–17.

Salaries and Stipends of Personnel Connected with the Ikhhlāsiyya Complex in Herat according to ʿAlī Shīr Navāʿī, *Vaqfiyya* (886/1481–82)

Profession or activity	Total number	Annually	
		Cash (altin)*	Kind (yūk)**
<i>mutavallī</i>	1	2000	20
<i>mudarris</i>	2	1200	24
<i>shaikh</i>	1	1000	10
<i>hāfiẓ</i> (best)	1	500	15
<i>vāʿiẓ</i>	1	500	10
<i>imām-khaṭīb</i>	1	500	10
<i>naukar</i>	2	500	5
<i>mushrif</i>	1	500	5
<i>ṣāhib-jam^c</i>	1	500	5
<i>ṭabbākh</i>	1	280	5
<i>ṭabaqchī</i>	1	200	5
<i>farrāsh</i>	1	200	5
<i>khādīm</i>	2	200	5
<i>muqrī</i>	1	200	5
<i>hāfiẓ</i> (other than best)	5	180	4
student:			
upper level	6	[288]	5
intermediate level	8	[192]	4
lower level	8	[144]	3

*i.e., *kapakī dīnār*

**i.e., 1 *kharvār* = 100 *mann*

Note: square brackets denote monthly stipend calculated on an annual basis

utensils, such as table cloths, pots, cups, plates, bowls, spoons.¹⁵⁰ Every night the servants and the concierge were to light candles in the halls (*dālān*) of the madrasa and the mosque and in the vestibules (*dihlīz*) of the Dār al-ḥuffāz and domed chamber of the khanaqah.¹⁵¹

The concierge, servants, server, and Koran reader of the khanaqah were responsible not only for clearing the snow in winter, but also for cleaning the water canal (*arigh*). After they dredged it and heaped the mud and sand from it onto its banks, the trustee was to hire laborers to cart it away.¹⁵² They were also required to keep the walkway that connected the madrasa and khanaqah over the Injil and that had been paved with

¹⁵⁰ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 17–18.

¹⁵¹ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 18–19.

¹⁵² V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 23–24.

stones in good repair so that people could pass freely between the two buildings.¹⁵³

Alī Shīr states as one of the conditions of his endowment that every thirty years the trustee was to make a new copy of the *Vaqfiyya* in order to prevent the text from becoming corrupted (*chürümägäy*) with the passage of time.¹⁵⁴ The fact that he required this new copy to be checked not only against the original (*aşl*), but also against the official Shari‘a court registers (*quzāt sijillāti*), underscores Alī Shīr’s earlier statement that it represented a summary (*mujmal*), in Turkish translation, of the original Persian *vaqf* documents.¹⁵⁵ Moreover, since it is clear from the context that by “*Vaqfiyya*” Alī Shīr was referring not just to those portions of his treatise that dealt with the Ikhlāş-iyya’s endowment, but to the entire treatise, this would have been another way of assuring the ultimate survival of the work.¹⁵⁶

Finally, Alī Shīr concludes with the standard prohibitions contained in *vaqf* documents of the period, namely, that the functionaries of the *şadr* (the government official charged with overseeing pious foundations) and the trustees not interfere (*madkhal qilmaghaylar*) in the foundation’s business (*sarkār*), that so long as the conditions set down by the endower are being fulfilled, they (presumably just the government officials) not demand to see its financial statement (*jam‘ va kharj nuskhasi*), nor take from its personnel anything they are not legally entitled to.¹⁵⁷ Although pious endowments were not entirely tax exempt, this is a reference to the broad administrative and fiscal immunity that they did enjoy. Official *vaqf* diplomas actually contained an enumeration of the taxes that the *vaqf* was being exempted from.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ENDOWED PROPERTIES

A summarized list of all the properties that had been converted into *vaqf*, the incomes from which were to be spent primarily on the two chief institutions of the complex—the madrasa and khanaqah, is provided by Alī Shīr in the *Vaqfiyya*.¹⁵⁸ He notes that all these

properties were his private property (*milk*),¹⁵⁹ and under his control and ownership for some time.¹⁶⁰ He states that he had observed the regulations of the Shari‘a in their purchase and that not a penny was left owing on them. The pious foundation he was establishing was therefore a legal one (*vaqf-i şahīṭ-i shar‘ī*), since it had satisfied the prescriptions of the Shari‘a for the establishment of *vaqf*.¹⁶¹

Alī Shīr divided the properties (to which he refers by the term, *maḥdūdāt*) into two categories: those in the city of Herat and those in its “dependencies” (*tavābi‘*) or surrounding regions. The list he provides of these properties represents one of the very rare extant documentary sources on the actual endowment of Timurid foundations. The properties within the city, that consisted of commercial real estate in the form of about 26 commercial structures located for the most part in or near the Malik bazar, the largest and most important of Herat’s markets, are as follows:¹⁶²

The Skull-cap sellers’ market (*Tāqīya furūshlar īmi*)¹⁶³ on the eastern side of the Malik bazar,¹⁶⁴ which is a two-storied (*iki ašam*) building and which, on the bazar side, has two passages (*darband*), each of which has a gate (*darvāza*) and a portico (*aivān*).

5 contiguous shops (*dukkān*) on the south side of this [Skull-cap sellers’] market and adjoining it.

A shop (*dukkān*) called “The Water Jug” (“*Khum-i āb*”) on the east side of the [Skull-cap sellers’] market; a felt seller’s shop with an upper floor (*bālākhāna*) on the western side of the [Malik] bazar; a leather seller’s

¹⁵⁹ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 10, where the word is actually vocalized. On the differences between *milk* and *mulk* and on the practice of their vocalization in original documents, see O. D. Chekhovich, “V. V. Bartol’d i puti dal’neishego issledovaniia problemy milka,” in *Formy feodal’noi zemel’noi sobstvennosti i vladenii na Blizhnem i Srednem Vostoke: Bartol’dovskie chteniia 1975 g.* (Moscow, 1979), 151–52.

¹⁶⁰ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 12.

¹⁶¹ V (GPB), fol. 116a, ll. 10–11.

¹⁶² V (GPB), fol. 117b, ll. 2–7.

¹⁶³ For the term *īm*, which she translates as “a trading premises” or “a kind of arcade of shops,” see Chekhovich, *Samarkandskie dokumenty*, 29.

¹⁶⁴ For the Malik bazar, see RJ, 1:78, where Isfizārī says that it has many *īms*, each of which elsewhere could have been a bazar in itself. See also Belenitskii, “Istoricheskaia topografiia,” 192, and Masson’s critique of the latter, “K istoricheskoii topografii,” 129.

¹⁵³ *Kim musulmānlarğa ötär barur dushvār bolmaghay*; V (GPB), fol. 118a, l. 25.

¹⁵⁴ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 26–27.

¹⁵⁵ V (GPB), fol. 118a, ll. 26–27.

¹⁵⁶ What is not clear, however, is whether the *Vaqfiyya* itself was also registered in the Shari‘a court registers.

¹⁵⁷ V (GPB), fol. 118a, l. 27–fol. 118b, l. 2; Levend, *Ali Şir*, 4:36.

¹⁵⁸ V (GPB), fol. 116a, l. 13.

shop also on the western side of the [Malik] bazar and also having an upper floor.

A small market (*tīmcha*) and 4 contiguous shops outside the ^cIrāq gate¹⁶⁵ opposite the ^cAlīka Beg baths.

A manufacturing warehouse (?) (*tīmcha* ^c*amalasi*) outside the Malik gate¹⁶⁶ [and] a two-storied building and 7 shops adjacent to it (i.e., the *tīmcha*).

A small market (*tīmcha*) and 2 shops adjacent to each other in the citadel (*quhunduz*) of Maṣrakh.¹⁶⁷

Two manufacturing shops (?) (*dukkān* ^c*amalasi*) in the Bāgh-i Zāghān lane (*kūcha*).¹⁶⁸

The properties outside the city—by far the greater majority—consisted of various types of land, including fields under grain cultivation (*mustaghall*), garden-orchards (*bāgh*), vineyards (*ūzūm bāgh*), and tracts of land (*yer*), as well as irrigation canals (*kārīz*), located in various districts (*bulūk*) and provinces (*vilāyat*) surrounding the city of Herat.¹⁶⁹

In the village (*mauzī*^c) of Farrāshān in the district (*bulūk*) of Ālanjān:¹⁷⁰ 25 *jarībs* of garden-orchard (*bāgh*); 23 *jarībs* contiguous to each other; a tract of

land (*yer*) measuring 17 *jarībs*, together with a garden, 2½ *jarībs* of which are a vineyard (*ūzūm bāgh*) known as “The Windmill” (“*Āsyā-yi bād*”); a plot of land (*bir qī*^c*a yer*) measuring 4½ *jarībs*.

In [the village of] Bād-i Murghān in the district (*bulūk*) of Injīl:¹⁷¹ 4 *jarībs*.

In the Khvāja Shihāb suburb (*maḥalla*) of [the village of] Siyāvashān [in the district (*bulūk*) of Gudāra]:¹⁷² gardens and 100 *jarībs* of land.

In the village (*kint*) of Sabad Ravān in the district (*bulūk*) of Sabqar:¹⁷³ 2 vineyards adjacent to each other [measuring] 12 *jarībs*; a garden [measuring] 4 *jarībs*.

In the suburb (*maḥalla*) of Suflā:¹⁷⁴ several garden plots [measuring] approximately 60 *jarībs*; in the same suburb, 26 *jarībs* of vineyard and 4 *jarībs* of land; a plot of land [measuring] 18 *jarībs*; 12 *jarībs* of garden; a garden [measuring] 19 *jarībs*; a garden with an adjoining plot of land [measuring] 10 *jarībs*; a vineyard measuring 4 *jarībs*; gardens and plots of irrigated land (?) (*yer raqabasi*) adjoining each other [and measuring] 74 *jarībs*, 34 *jarībs* of which are vineyard and the rest land; a plot of land with a vineyard adjacent to it

¹⁶⁵ This was the western gate of the city; Allen, *Catalogue*, 37.

¹⁶⁶ This was the northern gate of the city; Allen, *Catalogue*, 36. The meaning of *tīmcha* ^c*amalasi* is unclear. *Navoi asarlari lugati* (Tashkent, 1972), 44, only offers the explanation “workers” for ^c*amala*. Could this term possibly refer to a factory employing slave labor?

¹⁶⁷ This was the old citadel of Herat that already in the pre-Muslim era became an important burial ground; see Faṣīḥ-i Khvāfī [Fasikh Akhmad al-Khavafi], *Mujmal-i Faṣīḥī* [*Mudzhmal-i Fasikhi*], trans. D. Iu. Iusupova (Tashkent, 1980), 47; also RJ, 1:95.

¹⁶⁸ For the Kūcha-i Bāgh-i Zāghān, see Allen, *Catalogue*, 47, #88.

¹⁶⁹ V (GPB), fol. 116a, ll. 9–10; for the list, see fol. 117b, ll. 7–20.

¹⁷⁰ For the village of Farrāshān and the district of Ālanjān, which was south-west of Herat and noted for its orchard gardens, see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:25 (ed.); 2:83 (trans. and commentary). For the present-day location of Farrāshān, see Ludwig Adamec, *Historical and Political Gazetteer of Afghanistan*, 6 vols. (Graz: Akademische Druck und Verlangsanstalt, 1972–85), vol. 3: no entry, but indicated on map 8-C.

¹⁷¹ The *bulūk* of Injīl was the central district of Herat and was noted for its large number of palatial residences (^c*imārāt-i sarāhā*), pavilions (*kūshkhā*) and enclosed garden parks (*bāghāt*); Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:23–24. For Bād-i Murghān, see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:24 and 2:74, although its location is unidentified. It appears to the east of Herat on a map by Charles F. North, “Herat and its Environs. Surveyed in 1839–40,” India Office Library and Records. I am grateful to Terry Allen for kindly providing me with a photocopy of it.

¹⁷² See Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:23; 2:105 and 129. For *maḥalla* meaning “suburb,” see n. 76 above. For the present-day location of Siyāvashān, about 12 miles south-east of Herat, see Adamec, *Gazetteer*, 3:375. Isfizārī noted that it was famous for its high yield of grapes in some years; RJ, 1:83.

¹⁷³ The only other reference I have been able to find for Sabad Ravān is MA, fol. 176v, where it is mentioned as the place of retreat of the famous calligrapher/painter, Mīrak Naqqāsh. There was, however, a Safīd Ravān (also called Sa^cīd Ravān) south-east of Herat in the *bulūk* of Sabqar; see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:27 and 2:128.

¹⁷⁴ I have been unsuccessful in locating this toponym. It could refer to a suburb of the preceding village of Sabad Ravān.

[measuring] 5½ *jarībs*; a garden [measuring] 1½ *jarībs*; a garden [measuring] 4 *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 1½ *jarībs*; a garden [measuring] 8 *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 3 *jarībs*; several plots of land adjoining each other [and measuring] approximately 12 *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 4 *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 5 *jarībs*; a garden plot [measuring] 2½ *jarībs*; two gardens with an adjacent tract of land [measuring] 8 *jarībs*; a garden [measuring] 4 *jarībs*; several tracts of land adjacent to each other [measuring] 14 *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 1½ *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 24 *jarībs*; a plot of land [measuring] 1½ *jarībs*.

In the province (*vilāyat*) of Bādghīs:¹⁷⁵ the Tūdachi irrigation canal (*kārīz*) in its entirety.

In the district (*bulūk*) of Kamburāq:¹⁷⁶ the Paragach irrigation canal in its entirety.

In the village (*kint*) of Gul in the province (*vilāyat*) of Harārūd:¹⁷⁷ all the gardens, trees, and the residence (*sarāy*), together with its orchard (*bāghcha*) and other lands.¹⁷⁸

This comes to about 158 *jarībs* of garden-orchard (*bāgh*), 79 *jarībs* of vineyard and 282 *jarībs* of undifferentiated land (*yer*), making a total of approximately 519 *jarībs* in the districts surrounding Herat, not including those properties for which no measurements are given, such as the entire village of Gul which actually

¹⁷⁵ For the province of Bādghīs, which was noted for its springs, rivers and irrigation canals, see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:31–32 and 2:29–30; also Adamec, *Gazetteer*, 3:33ff. For a discussion of its agricultural products during Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā's reign, see A. A. Semenov, "Nekotorye dannye po ekonomike imperii Sultana Khusein-Mirzy (1469–1506)," *Izvestiia Otdeleniia obshchestvennykh nauk Akademii nauk Tadzhikskoi SSR*, 4 (1953): 73–75.

¹⁷⁶ For the Kamburāq district, which was south-east of Herat and south of the Harārūd river, see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:28 and 2:27.

¹⁷⁷ For the village of Gul, see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:30 and 2:91. For *kint* (= *qarya*), see E. A. Davidovich, "Feodal'nyi zemel'nyi milk v Srednei Azii XV–XVIII vv.: Sushchnost' i transformatsiia," in *Formy feodal'noi zemel'noi sobstvennosti*, 52.

¹⁷⁸ V (GPB II), fols. 221a–221b contains only very minor and insignificant variations in the sizes of the properties cited.

consisted of 14 hamlets (*mazra'a*) and the lands belonging to them.¹⁷⁹

It is difficult to establish exactly the size of the *jarīb* as a unit of measurement of land area in eastern Khorasan in the second half of the 15th century because it varied considerably from locality to locality. Generally speaking, in medieval Iran and Central Asia, it measured 60 *gaz* x 60 *gaz* (i.e., 3600 sq. *gaz*).¹⁸⁰ According to the Soviet scholar, O. D. Chekhovich, who studied the landholding of the Samarkand region of the second half of the 15th century on the basis of *vaqf* documents, the *jarīb* (which was also called *janāb* in Central Asia), equalled approximately 2500 sq. m.¹⁸¹ According to the standard work on Islamic metrology by Hinz, the *jarīb* in the Iranian cultural sphere in the late medieval period was the equivalent of approx. 1600 sq. m. which by the 17th century had become reduced to approx. 960 sq. m.¹⁸² In 19th-century Central Asia, the *jarīb* varied between 1707 and 4097 sq. m.¹⁸³ In 20th-century Iran, it could be anywhere from 400 to 1450 sq. m.,¹⁸⁴ while in Afghanistan it measured approximately 1950 sq. m.¹⁸⁵ If one accepts Chekhovich's figure of 2500 sq. m. for the *jarīb*, the total land area that ʿAlī Shīr provided measurements for in his *Vaqfiyya* can be

¹⁷⁹ Thus according to Ḥāfiẓ-i Abrū—see Krawulsky, *Horāsān*, 1:30. For the term *mazra'a*, and the difference between it and *qarya* (= *kint*), see Petrushevskii, *Zemledelie*, 290–98.

¹⁸⁰ RJ, 1:329. See also E. A. Davidovich, "Materialy po metrologii srednevekovoi Srednei Azii," in V. Khints [W. Hinz], *Musul'manskie mery i vesa s perevodom v metricheskuiu sistemu*, trans. and expanded Iu. È. Bregel' (Moscow, 1970), 122; also Petrushevskii, *Zemledelie*, 100. Determining the length of the *gaz*, however, presents a major problem.

¹⁸¹ See Chekhovich, *Samarkandskie dokumenty*, 24 and 381, n. 22.

¹⁸² Khints [Hinz], *Musul'manskie mery*, 73; elsewhere (p. 43), on the basis of a statement made by Daulatshāh that 1 *jarīb* of land produced 4 *kharvārs* of grain in the time of Ulūgh Beg, Hinz gives the figure of 958 sq. m. for the *jarīb* in Turkestan (= Transoxiana) in the first half of the 15th century, but he seems to contradict himself when he says that this could only have been possible if the *kharvār* were the older, smaller *kharvār* which weighed only 83.3 kg. From other sources, however, we know that the Herati *kharvār* weighed 300 kg. and therefore, the size of the *jarīb* in Daulatshāh's reference had to be considerably larger. For the *kharvār*, see below.

¹⁸³ Davidovich, "Materialy," 126–28.

¹⁸⁴ Lambton, *Landlord and Peasant*, 407.

¹⁸⁵ Since the *gaz-i jarīb* equalled 736 m. See Adamec, *Gazetteer*, 3:x.

calculated at approximately 325 acres. If, on the other hand, the lower figure of 1600 sq. m. given by Hinz is taken, the total acreage of the properties mentioned in the *Vaqfiyya* would be approximately 205.

VALUE OF THE ENDOWMENT

Although these figures provide some idea of the size of the landed properties that ʿAlī Shīr was bequeathing to the complex, they are not especially significant for our purposes, since it was not the land itself or the shops, bazars, irrigation canals, etc., that actually constituted the endowment, but the income from them (after the requisite payment of taxes).¹⁸⁶ Despite the fact that ʿAlī Shīr does not cite revenue figures directly in the *Vaqfiyya*, based on the currency figures he does give for the salaries that were to be paid to the personnel of the complex and for the expenditures associated with its maintenance, as well as the figures for the weight of the grain and food that was to be distributed to the poor and that constituted that portion of salaries that was to be paid out in kind, it is possible to estimate what that income must have been at its very minimum.

First of all, based on the personnel that ʿAlī Shīr enumerates in the *Vaqfiyya*, it is clear that the Ikhlaṣiyya's endowment had to support at least 44 people. The amounts that ʿAlī Shīr stipulated were to be spent annually in cash were 15,496 *altins* for salaries and stipends and 400 *altins* for furnishings, giving a total of at least 15,896 *altins* annually. If we estimate that the cost of the 600-odd articles of clothing that were also to be distributed, as well as of the maintenance that he does not specify, must have been, say, 4000 *altins*, this would give a total of about 19,896 *altins*.

Exactly what monetary unit ʿAlī Shīr intended by *altin* is not clear. Technically, it designated a gold coin. The currency of Timurid Khorasan, however, was based on silver, the most typical monetary unit being the *kapakī dīnār* which designated a silver coin.¹⁸⁷ Six *kapakī dīnārs* made up the *tanga*,¹⁸⁸ which in Ḥusain Bāyqarā's Herat weighed 4.8 gm. silver.¹⁸⁹ Although

there were gold coins in circulation in Khorasan in the second half of the 15th century, it is very unlikely that they would have been used to pay the salaries and stipends of the personnel of a pious endowment. Ordinarily, these were paid in silver coin on an annual basis, and in copper coin on a daily basis¹⁹⁰ (1 *kapakī dīnār* being made up of 6 copper *dīnārs*, sometimes called "Herati *dīnārs*").¹⁹¹

If we assume that by *altin* ʿAlī Shīr meant the *kapakī dīnār* and compare the salaries and stipends of some of the personnel of the Ikhlaṣiyya complex with the salaries and stipends of those in similar institutions at the end of the 15th and beginning of the 16th centuries, we can see that they were comparable. Thus, for example, the annual salary of the professors at the Ikhlaṣiyya madrasa, which was 1200 *altins* (i.e., *kapakī dīnārs*), was the same as that of one of the professors at the madrasa of Muḥammad Shībānī Khān in Samarkand cited in a *vaqf-nāma* of the first quarter of the 16th century, while that of another was much lower at 800 *kapakī dīnārs*.¹⁹² This confirms the fact that ʿAlī Shīr,

Iran, vol. 6: *The Timurid and Safavid Periods*, ed. Peter Jackson and Laurence Lockhart (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986), 567, it weighed 4.72 gm.

¹⁹⁰ See Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 282.

¹⁹¹ Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 49.

¹⁹² See Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 284, table 34 (where 7200 and 4800 copper *dīnārs* were the equivalent of 1200 and 800 *kapakī dīnārs* respectively). Generally speaking, the Ikhlaṣiyya staff and students seemed to have fared much better than their counterparts in madrasas in Transoxiana. Their salaries and stipends were higher not only in cash, but also in kind. Thus, for example, whereas the two Ikhlaṣiyya professors received 24 loads (*yük*) of grain annually, which weighed 2400 *mann*, the equivalent of 7200 kg. (for the Herati *mann*, see n. 190 below), their two counterparts in Samarkand received 300 and 250 *mann*, or 6000 and 5000 kg., respectively (since the Samarkandi *mann* weighed about 20 kg. compared with the Herati *mann* at 3 kg.; see Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 289). As for the students at the Ikhlaṣiyya, they were relatively speaking even better off. While the stipends of those at the three academic levels, calculated on an annual basis, were 288, 192 and 144 *altins* (i.e., *kapakī dīnārs*) in cash, respectively, and 1500, 1200 and 900 kg. of grain (the equivalent of 500, 400 and 300 Herati *mann*), respectively, in kind, those of their counterparts in Samarkand were only 90, 60 and 50 *kapakī dīnārs* (the equivalent of 540, 360 and 300 copper *dīnārs*) in cash, and 1200, 900 and 600 kg. (the equivalent of 60, 45 and 30 Samarkandi *mann*) in kind for the three academic levels, respectively. Although those members of the Ikhlaṣiyya staff who received large amounts of grain as salaries in kind must

¹⁸⁶ On this point, see Davidovich, "Feodal'nyi zemel'nyi milk," 53.

¹⁸⁷ E. A. Davidovich, *Istoriia denezhnogo obrashcheniia srednevekovoi Srednei Azii* (Moscow, 1983), 56.

¹⁸⁸ Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 47 (based on HS); but, according to data contained in other sources, the *tanga* consisted of 3 *kapakī dīnārs*; Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 49.

¹⁸⁹ E. A. Davidovich, "Sviditel'stvo Daulatshakha o razmerakh zemel'noi renty pri Ulugbeke," *Pis'mennye pamiatniki Vostoka* (1971): 26. According to *The Cambridge History of*

who consistently used the Turkic equivalents of Persian terms throughout the *Vaqfiyya* (as in his use of *yük* instead of the more common Persian *kharvār*, for example¹⁹³), simply used the Chaghatay Turkic equivalent of the term *dīnār* (which had in the past designated a gold coin), namely *altin* (which likewise meant a gold coin), while by the “generic” term *dīnār* he intended the *kapakī dīnār* that was typical of the late Timurid period.

As for the weight of food and grain required annually by the complex, this included 245 *yük* (= *kharvār*), weighing 24,500 *mann*¹⁹⁴ for salaries and stipends in kind, and at least 10,680 *batman* (= *mann*) for distribution to the poor, giving a minimum total weight of about 35,180 *mann*, roughly the equivalent of 105,540 kg.¹⁹⁵ This does not include various miscellaneous items, such as the sheep, cow, etc., that ʿAlī Shīr also mentioned but for which no *batman* figure is given. Unfortunately, we do not know the price of a *yük* (*kharvār*) or *batman* (*mann*) of grain in Herat at the end of the 15th century to enable us to calculate this total figure in *kapakī dīnārs*. However, according to the calculations made by the Soviet economic historian, Elena Davidovich, on the basis of rates of pay in cash and kind in various *vaqf* documents from Transoxiana (esp. Bukhara and Samarkand) in the mid-15th and beginning of the 16th centuries, a kg. of grain (undifferentiated) cost approximately 3 copper *dīnārs* (= .5 *kapakī dīnārs*).¹⁹⁶ This would mean that the total cost of grain and food that was required by the complex to satisfy the conditions of its endowment was, very approximately, 52,770 *kapakī dīnārs*.

Thus, the total minimum income that ʿAlī Shīr’s endowment had to produce yearly in order to maintain the Ikhilāsiyya complex was about 73,000 *kapakī dīnārs*. To put this figure into some perspective, a home near

have had a greater number of dependents to support, they still must have been left with a surplus which could be sold, since the minimum daily requirement of grain for one person was about 1.7 kg. (according to Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 284).

¹⁹³ An even more striking example is his use of the Mongolian word *ebüge* for grandfather in the phrase, *ata ebügam* (“my father and grandfather”); V (GPB), fol. 113b, l. 13.

¹⁹⁴ The *yük/kharvār* equalled 100 *mann* (= *batman*); see Khints [Hinz], *Musulmanskie mery*, 43.

¹⁹⁵ The Herati *mann* weighed about 3 kg.; see Khints [Hinz], *Musulmanskie mery*, 28; 3.7 kg. according to Petrushevskii, *Zemledelie*, 72.

¹⁹⁶ See Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 288. She also calculated the figure of 1.3 copper *dīnārs* (= 0.2 *kapakī dīnārs*) for 1 kg. of grain at the end of the 16th century; Davidovich, *Istoriia*, 289.

the Ikhilāsiyya madrasa that one of its professors, Amīr Burhān al-Dīn ʿAtāʾullāh, attempted to buy cost 3000 *kapakī dīnārs*.¹⁹⁷ The actual value of the endowment was naturally far higher than the figure of 73,000 *kapakī dīnārs*, since not only does it not take into account the revenues from the markets, shops, irrigation canals, etc., for which no revenue figures are provided and which must have been considerable, but also because we do not know just how much the landed properties actually yielded.

Given the incomplete nature of the data contained in the *Vaqfiyya* and in other sources of the period, any estimate of the value of the Ikhilāsiyya’s endowment must necessarily remain a gross approximation. Nonetheless, the figure of 73,000 *kapakī dīnārs* which represents an estimate of the minimum value of the endowment provides some insight into the immense size of all of ʿAlī Shīr’s personal property, since even if the actual size of the Ikhilāsiyya’s endowment was five times this figure, it still would not have represented more than about 7% of all of ʿAlī Shīr’s endowments in Khorasan, the total value of which Daulatshāh put at 5 million *kapakī dīnārs*.¹⁹⁸

CONCLUSION

The *Vaqfiyya* of ʿAlī Shīr Navāʾī highlights the activities of what its author considered the two most important components of the complex he built and endowed—the madrasa and khanaqah. Completed by 886/1481–82,¹⁹⁹ the Ikhilāsiyya madrasa and its supporting Khalāsiyya khanaqah ranked in importance

¹⁹⁷ Although it actually went for a somewhat higher price; see MA, fol. 170r.

¹⁹⁸ See reference, n. 12 above.

¹⁹⁹ The date of 1475 for the Ikhilāsiyya’s completion given by Golombek and Wilber (*Timurid Architecture*, I:448, #56) is incorrect. It will be recalled that ʿAlī Shīr only received the land on which he built the complex in 881/1476–77. Moreover, in the versified colophon of the *Vaqfiyya*, ʿAlī Shīr suggests that the buildings had only been completed by 886/1481–82 [see V (GPB), fol. 118b; V (GPB II), fol. 224b):

A hundred thanks [to God] that the buildings have been completed (*mukammal*)!

Their endowment was detailed [above].

Eight hundred and eighty-six was the date

On which their diploma of endowment (*vaqfiyyasi*) was officially registered (*musajjal*).

Since the terminus post quem is 881 and the terminus ante quem 886, the complex must have been completed in about five years or less.

with the finest educational ensembles of Herat: the madrasa-mosque of Gauhar Shād (dating from the first half of the 15th century) located northwest of the city and south of the Injil canal; Shāhrukh's madrasa-khanaqah in the city (also dating from the first half of the century); the ancient Ghiyāsiyya madrasa in the city dating back to Kartid times;²⁰⁰ and the madrasa-khanaqah of Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā, which was completed in 898/1492–93,²⁰¹ and which, like the Ikhlāsiyya ensemble, straddled the Injil canal.

According to Khvāndamīr, there were seven professors teaching in the Ikhlāsiyya around the year 1500,²⁰² compared with eight in Ḥusain Bāyqarā's madrasa, four in Shāhrukh's, and four in Gauhar Shād's.²⁰³ The

concentration of these three educational complexes in the northern suburbs of Herat, all built during the reign of the Timurids and all exceptionally well endowed,²⁰⁴ is eloquent testimony not only to the pre-occupation of the Timurid period with learning and the arts, but also to the central role of the pious endowment (*vaqf*) in the Timurid system of cultural patronage. In his *apologia*, Sultan Ḥusain Bāyqarā boasted of the fact that, during his reign, the pious endowments that under previous rulers had been allowed to go to ruin, were all restored and that there were in Herat nearly one hundred educational institutions (*ḥauza-i dars*) all supported by income from *auqāf*.²⁰⁵ Unlike its companion madrasas, however, whose *vaqfiyyas* have not survived and about whose endowments and activities we are not nearly as well informed, the halls and courtyards of the Ikhlāsiyya complex, thanks to ʿAlī Shīr's *Vaqfiyya*, still seem to reverberate with the sound of its students, Sufis and myriad guests, even so many centuries after Timurid times.

²⁰⁰ See Allen, *Catalogue*, 131.

²⁰¹ O'Kane, *Timurid Architecture*, 339. Since ʿAlī Shīr describes Ḥusain Bāyqarā's madrasa in the *Vaqfiyya* [V (GPB), fol. 115b], either it was not yet entirely completed at the time (in which case it took a very long time to build), or else the date of its completion was earlier than 898/1492–93.

²⁰² KhA, 19. The *Khulāṣat al-akhbār* was completed in 905/1499–1500.

²⁰³ KhA, 15 and 17. As for the Ghiyāsiyya, according to its *vaqfiyya*, the most learned religious scholar in all of Khorasan was to be appointed to teach in it; HS, 4:343.

²⁰⁴ Thus according to KhA, 17.

²⁰⁵ Tourkhan Gandjei, "Uno scritto apologetico di Ḥusain Mīrā, Sultano del Khorāsān," *Annali dell'Istituto Universitario Orientale di Napoli*, n.s., 5 (1954): 169, ll. 13–21.

در روزی در سکرته کیم آن لام دیک قدیم دایا شود بوبین نور تو بی زکات و در بی نیم نوری اول تکیه زکات کیم که بخونم کا
 نصاب قریه میگویند مال ذخیره یعنی فی سنین ساله ای نصاب قریه کسان مال زکاتین آیم نه پو امیکم و اما فی پیشین حج در روز
 اول بی عزیزی مستور بولامین ما نا که اسلام شخصی پر کیشی کا ادخار زکیم آژاوا اسر سبب دین نورنی بار و بس معزز و در کیم
 بیش لای حواسیم دایکم بر لاسه موجب نصابی بر لور و بود که بر بونان ایکی آرزو دین پر به بر بار ک سفره در راهیوم امیکم
 اسلام شخصی پیش مرتین پر ی نیک و کس کس که بی دین ناقص بولما غای و مسلمان لیتم تجسی پر بار واقف بر غلوی سببی دین
 منقول قالما غای اول عادت آیین فاند کیم اول بادید ساری کیم شامی جویا برید اسر اب بیاتی چینه نیات زلالی و اول لال
 اطیاند اسر نیلان بوته سی کلشن نجات غانی در عزیت قیلد اگر قاندلسا لارین چزی سایه سید ایر باهام بر یوزید اسای
 جسمندی و اول زک کیمیدی دین قر تو لب اول فاند ایریشام و اگر میر حاج لیت محلی حمید امکم ران بولالاسام جسم کیم
 چاک کسوم و اصطر اب لیت کسوم دین نقان تار تیب اول محل طینی مقصده نیشام سینی کیم بوسود انزار ایادی
 سوسن کیمه اپنار ایادی فی الحاکم که تپانی زار سکون پر اد کیم بونکر ایکی تانی زون ار در سنین قدم تا که با دهنی کام
 کورنی سینه کسکه در سبک کام اگر بولد بولد انورم نیشام چو بولد اول در اول ام ار در سنین و کورولم اول زک کیم به بهر مند
 زکی کاید دینت بند و در مقدمات دین عرض بویکم اول سبب سبب اول در دید اسر کدر اول قند خورشید مثال
 طریقه آوره و ار ایورده لوزد افراق ز پیری و استیقا سلسله سید اعلقه بونان قدیمی توار تیب اول مسند شیک کیمیدی قد
 ایکیک فی طلب ایستام و حضرت نیک بود اقبال و کجود آمل ایک در کای نیک ثابت دوا می او چون دعا بقان بین و کیشی
 مرادیم اول کیم اعلی حضرت نیک ثابت سیز فایت لاری و نهایت سیز شفت لاری مغایر سید ایوتاری مذکور و صدرا مسطر
 بونان خدمت لار دین بو تیر کیم بویجه و طریقه حضرت سبب ات خدمت اول ایردی کیم زیاده اوقاتم و خلاصه ریاستی
 اول حضرت نیک حج ذاتی توبین سفایتد امر ف تقسام ایردی داد لوب و اغراضیده لار در کین خول لار و مطبوع شد لار
 در صنوع انش لار بلکه مرفوع نظم و نثر وین کتاب لار تصنیف قیلد ایردی و مجلد لار ترتیب پر سام ایردی اول حضرت نیک
 فرخنده آتی بر سید پلدر کپیل لار روزگار و حیف سید مذکور و ما یون ذاتی بود اسله پلدر کپیل لار در روزگار ای
 تیلی و مذکور بولد ایردی ابوجهت دین کیم اول حضرت نیک بس که الشافی عمادیت اهتمام یا سوزی بو خاک رود زک کیم
 نازل و اوقات سبب سیزین انشانت شالی بوی ترا حالته شالی در ایل نیک تره و ای او کس اعلی انزال معلق
 و اثرات اشاطی و فرائض اگر امی و حوام توغاشی عالم ارای و مظلوم علالسی رعایا عطوی دیما سلیج بار خوشی طبع اعلی نیک موار
 ملایمی و طلب خلی نیک تا جبار ملازمی جمال سخی دین سیشوه سی خرابانان لار نیک سو که ایرینی و عمل نقلی دین دور کادی
 خرابانان لار نیک ستر ایرینی بو در مخلوق عذاب خاندان لار نیک بولدم باشید اقور ما علیی و فرزندان کرد قریبان لار نیک
 ایانیم کای ایک اور ما علیی و انما بس این طلب نیک عرضداشت و قدوسی و خلکت شمار شرا نیک نصد و مقلوبی لالت لارین
 کیکلار در ماذه لارانی نیک نیشی و آله فی رضا لاری پله او ذاق نیک شیشی سر حد یک لار ایلی سی قاننی نیک زقی
 و آله فی و لاه لاری پله قانن رفاق نیک محنی او ذکا خلکت دین آزه آرزو میا نین نیک طبع خوار یعنی اول لار کجا قر تو لب

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کسان

‘Alī Shīr Navā’ī, *Vaqfiyya*, Leningrad, Saltykov-Shchedrin State Public Library, Khanykov Collection, 55 (904/1498-99), fols. 116b-118b. Reproduced by permission.

مصلحت بود و در دکان نام حضورید که در کتب توبه مذکور است و در حجاج دخی آذین کعبه بسهم قیامی را در بکلیه این
 اوج سادوم برادر اجمالی طریقی سید در اهل حدود است این اول حدودی دور که شمس در اهلکایاری ایند استرق صدی و اسیر طایفه
 تری فر دور و عاری ایکی شام دور و باز ساری ایکی در بندای باره در بندای ابر در ازده متوجه بود در بریم شمس جنبی حدی
 پیش دکان بر پر یک متصل یا نه دکان کیم جماعت خستور دور تم نیک شرقی صدی و اهر در دوشکون دکانی بلا فغانی مله هم در نایک
 غربی سید اهر پر بستین در شش کانی هم بار بار از نیک غربی سید ابالا فغانی سید یا نه پر چه دورت دکان بر پر یک متصل عراق در از
 پی سید اهلک یک عمای خدای تو یا نه پر یک عده سی ملک در ازده سی باشد ایکی شام عارت اسکیزه دکان چه در دکان
 یا نه پر یک دکان بر پر یک متصل صحن نیک قندزید ایانا ایکی دکان عده سی باغ زاغان کوچه سید اوج دور و عده است کیم
 شرفی دکانی داد در آفتاب بود که افزاش نوضی و ایگری پیش بر پیش ایگری اوج جیب بر پر یک متصل یا نه پر طلع باغ پند
 بران اسکیزه جیب کیم آذین ایکی اهریم جیب اوزدم باغی آسیای باه خستور دور و در طلع بر نورت جیب بر پر نیواغیل بویکین
 با در عان و اورت جیب سیدان دین خرابه شایب عده سید آباغات و یوز جیب بر سبزه بود که
 سید در ان کستی و ایکی طلع اوزدم باغی هم بر پر یک تو شمس اوان ایکی جیب یا نه پر باغ نورت جیب یا نه شعی ملک سید
 بخند باغات آتیش جیب خیم یا نه ذکر محمد ایگری آتی جیب اوزدم باغی دورت جیب بر یا نه پر طلع اوان اسکیزه
 دانی اوان ایکی جیب یا نه پر طلع اوان نورت جیب یا نه پر طلع یا نه پر طلع اوان جیب یا نه پر طلع اوان نورت
 یا نه باغات پند بر بدی دهفات پند کیم بر پر یک تو شمس اوان در پیش دورت جیب کیم آذین دورت جیب اوزدم باغی
 ۱۰۱ زکای بر بولهای یا نه پر طلع بر دکان تو شمس پیش اهریم جیب یا نه پر باغ جیب و دانی نیز بر باغ نورت جیب یا نه پر طلع
 بر جیب دجه در ایکن یا نه پر طلع یا اسکیزه جیب یا نه پر طلع بر اوج جیب یا نه پر طلع بر پر پر یک تو شمس اوان ایکی جیب
 یا نه پر طلع بر نورت جیب یا نه پر طلع بر پیش جیب یا نه پر طلع باغ ایکی اهریم جیب یا نه ایکی طلع باغ بر تو شمس اسکیزه جیب یا نه
 طلع باغ نورت جیب یا نه پر طلع بر تو شمس اوان نورت جیب یا نه پر طلع بر پر جیب دجه در ایکن یا نه پر طلع بر یکری نورت
 جیب یا نه پر طلع بر اهریم جیب دجه در ایکن لایق و اودی کایری تمام کال پند دکه اوق بود که اهریم کایری مکن بر ازده
 دلاقی و اکل کیتی جمع باغات و درختان در سایر باغ و سایر اراضی سی پند بوجع حدود است کیم حدودی دغه لار داکر مذکور
 بر بورتور افی بود اهر اتمه بل سیدی موقعا سی مذکور بر لمان تلع ذوقت جمع شهری عیله ی ارباب و طبایف ایکی عالم شعی در رس
 بر نای بری نیک لایق و طیفه سی نیک ایکی یوز آتون نغده یگیری دورت آیش کیم شعی آریه شانی بوغدای بونی بر علف و در رس
 اوان مطب ملک کیم باسی یگیری ایکی بونی ایقی اعلی بر پر یک ای بقی نغده یگیری دورت آتون بیلد بوغدای پیش و کلا وسط اسکیزه
 ایلیج بر پر یک نغده اوان آتی آتون بوغدای بیلین دورت یوک اوان اسکیزه ایلیج بر پر یک نغده اوان ایکی آتون شعی بیل
 اوج یوک آتی خوشوان حافظ دین صدره خیل بقی نغده پیش یوز آتون سانسند اشلیج اوان پیش یوک پیش سایدین بر پر یک
 بیلین نغده یوز یکسان آتون بوغدای دورت یوک شعی ذیل بقی نغده یک آتون سانسند اشلیج اوان یوک اطف ذیل بقی
 نغده پیش یوز آتون بوغدای اوان یوک سزی ذیل بقی نغده ایکی یوز آتون بوغدای پیش یوک خاتمه طبایف نیک بیل بونی
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 نغده

کسیان نورت جیب

هر مثل متغای لار با ام که شرط واقف پدموافق علی یقینای لار بوسه کار علم سیرین جمع و فوج ~~توسعه~~ لار
 و هیچ نفع آلا ردین آلمانای لار کیم آلا ر خد مال و مباح ایما سس چون بر غیر مذکور برهان مکتب اوقاف ابرکانی کا
 اقرار قلب پریشی تفرین کیم اوز بقیلم دین متوال قلب ایدوم قدردوم مناسه عظام مرانده شرعی صغینه اوجنت مکی قلب
 بو عدد و اوقاف از جملاتی پند سرخ و اوز تویتعانی پلسو سغ قلب بوقاع مذمذمه مو بد وقت برهان من مستقیم تفرید و بد
 عالم ایستدین سی حوالات یا ~~بیا~~ فزایکا کی تازتا ر نه حوالات یا ~~بیا~~ هم بین رن پل جدول ایت یا ~~بیا~~ برز شکر گنده لار شکل بر لاری
 و تخی بر عدد کیم فصل بود ~~بیا~~ سیکتیز ایدنی سیکتانی نایج ~~بیا~~ بقیه سی اهل کور کوسجل بر لاری ~~بیا~~ و بقیه کرتا رندی سی نعمت انج
 تبولدی شرط خطیرین نیت انج ~~بیا~~ شرط اید کیم قلبه عمل ~~بیا~~ اولکیم موخا تیز برور نعمت انج ~~بیا~~ برحقا عددنی کیم کرتوا با برسون
 نیکو عمارات و انج یا رادسون ~~بیا~~ کیم برز سر برز و علونده نرا ابرسون
 قنوت و تفرین کرتا رادسون ~~بیا~~ آسین برب الله بن